

D3.1: Simulation workflows and MODA sheets

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*PU Public

PP Restricted to other programme participants (incl. Commission Services)

RE Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (incl. Commission Services)

CO Confidential, only for the members of the consortium (incl. Commission Services)

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List of Acronyms

BEM	Boundary Element Method
C4P	Carbo4Power
CF	Carbon Fibre
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
DOF	Degree of Freedom
EMMC	European Materials Modelling Council
FE /M	Finite Element / Method
FRP	Fibre Reinforced Polymer
GF	Glass Fibre
MODA	Modelling Data
MR	Material Relation
NE	Nano-Engineered
PE	Physics Equation
RANS	Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes
RTM	Resin Transfer Moulding
RVE	Representative Volume Element
TTB	Tidal Turbine Blade
UD	Unidirectional
WP	Work Package
WTB	Wind Turbine Blade

Executive Summary

Carbo4Power's main objective is to develop a new generation of lightweight, high strength, multifunctional, digitalized multi-materials for offshore turbine rotor blades (WTB & TTB) that will increase their operational performance and durability while reducing cost of energy production, maintenance and their environmental impact.

Modelling and simulation activities have been proposed in the project to support the analysis, design and optimization of the turbine blades. In addition, these activities will also support the development of new materials, coatings, joints and repairs.

This report collects the MODelling DATA (MODA) sheets prepared by WP3 partners for each simulation planned to be developed in C4P. The main purpose of it is to define the workflows, the inputs / outputs, the physics involved, the material relations and the methodologies / computational implementation of each individual model. In addition, the interactions between the different models are described.

1 Introduction

The modelling activities proposed in Carbo4Power are mostly integrated in *WP3: Modelling and Design*. These activities give support in many of the developments proposed in terms of materials, coatings, modular blades solutions and joining techniques. It will also help with the design/definition of the prototypes and demonstrators and the analysis of the blades at full scale.

The modelling activities are planned to be executed following the recommendations of the EMMC (European Materials Modelling Council, <https://emmc.info/>), which include the development of the MODelling DATA sheets (MODAs). The objective of MODAs is to establish a common terminology in materials modelling which leads to simplified and more efficient communication.

Under this consideration, a specific task has been created within WP3, *Task3.1: Definition of simulation work-flows and MODAs*. One MODA sheet has been prepared for each simulation, following the common data structure proposed by the Council to define/describe any material modelling simulation. The purpose of these documents is to define the models with a standard data organization covering the following aspects:

- 1) Overview of the simulation
- 2) Workflow
- 3) Aspect of the User Case or System simulated with this model
- 4) Model
- 5) Computational aspects
- 6) Post processing

Based on this information, the fiches should contain all elements needed to describe a simulation. This information spans from the end-user (manufacturer) information to the computational modelling details.

Simulation work-flows are defined to establish the links of the modelling activities with the rest of WPs through the identification of the inputs and outputs.

All MODA sheets are included in the next section. The amount and relevant information of the simulations covered by these fiches is resumed in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1 Simulations covered by the MODA sheets

Type of simulation	Partner	Related Task	Number of models in the MODA sheet
Modelling to support NE materials for thermal heaters	<i>HAY</i>	<i>3.2.1</i>	<i>3</i>
Modelling to support analysis of different CF treatments	<i>ITA</i>	<i>3.2.2</i>	<i>2</i>
Simulation of RTM processes for TTB demonstrator	<i>ITA</i>	<i>3.2.3</i>	<i>1</i>
Models for Bladelet-tip design for WTB	<i>BIO</i>	<i>3.3</i>	<i>3</i>
Modelling coatings and their effects in WTB/TTB performance	<i>BST</i>	<i>3.4</i>	<i>2</i>

Type of simulation	Partner	Related Task	Number of models in the MODA sheet
Models for Design and analysis of WTB	<i>ORE</i>	3.5	2
Models for Design and analysis of intra-modular joints and repairs	<i>ITA</i>	3.6	3
Models for Design and analysis of prototypes, demonstrators and full blades analyses	<i>UoS</i>	3.7	2

2 MODA sheets

Eight MODA fiches are included in the present deliverable:

- [1] Modelling to support NE materials for thermal heaters (HAY)
- [2] Modelling to support analysis of different CF treatments (ITAINNOVA)
- [3] Simulation of RTM processes for TTB demonstrator (ITAINNOVA)
- [4] Models for Bladelet-tip design for WTB (BIOG3D)
- [5] Modelling coatings and their effects in WTB/TTB performance (BST)
- [6] Models for Design and analysis of WTB (ORE)
- [7] Models for Design and analysis of intra-modular joints and repairs (ITAINNOVA)
- [8] Models for Design and analysis of prototypes, demonstrators and full blades analyses (UoS)

The fiches are detailed individually in the next sub-sections.

2.1 Modelling to support NE materials for thermal heaters

MODA
MOdelling DAta providing a description
for Model to support NE materials for thermal heaters – Task 3.2.1
CARBO4POWER

Romilly Close, Haydale Composite Solutions, romilly.close@haydale.com

OVERVIEW of the SIMULATION									
1	<p style="text-align: center;">USER CASE</p> <p>The goal is to estimate the required power output of nanomaterial-enhanced heaters to maintain a wind turbine blade temperature above a set temperature while undergoing realistic external wind conditions.</p>								
2	<p style="text-align: center;">CHAIN OF MODELS</p> <table border="1" style="width: 100%; border-collapse: collapse;"> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">MODEL 1</td> <td>Effect of load on ink temperature</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">MODEL 2</td> <td>Heat conduction through composite</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">MODEL 3</td> <td>Heat up of surface with thermal emission to atmosphere</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">DATA MINING METHODOLOGY</td> <td>N/A</td> </tr> </table>	MODEL 1	Effect of load on ink temperature	MODEL 2	Heat conduction through composite	MODEL 3	Heat up of surface with thermal emission to atmosphere	DATA MINING METHODOLOGY	N/A
MODEL 1	Effect of load on ink temperature								
MODEL 2	Heat conduction through composite								
MODEL 3	Heat up of surface with thermal emission to atmosphere								
DATA MINING METHODOLOGY	N/A								
3	<p style="text-align: center;">PUBLICATION PEER-REVIEWING THE DATA</p> <p>N/A</p>								
4	<p style="text-align: center;">ACCESS CONDITIONS</p> <p>All data is generated and reserved by Haydale Composite Solutions.</p>								
5	<p style="text-align: center;">WORKFLOW AND ITS RATIONALE</p> <p>A macro-scale simulation strategy is proposed (represented in the workflow diagram). This is due to the limitations of modelling nanomaterials. Inputs shall instead be constructed from a robust data set that has been produced by HCS internally.</p> <p>Initially, the inks shall be represented as a unit area with bulk properties. Later models will increase the modelling scale and consider the system-wide effects.</p>								

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Workflow picture

User case input

Model

Raw Output

Processed output

Continuum models

Heater Print Geometry

Figure 2.1 Workflow of Modelling to support NE materials for thermal heaters – Task 3.2.1

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MODA

Physics-based Model

Simulation with MODEL 1 - Heater Print Geometry

1 ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED		
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	This model will be used to simulate the resistance of the heater for different geometries and the power required for heating. The model will include different inks and deposition thicknesses. The heat up rate will be calculated for each geometry.
1.2	MATERIAL	Functionalised nanomaterial in polymer ink carrier
1.3	GEOMETRY	The modelling will be performed on printed heater tracks with different layout within the circuit (such as x heater tracks in series, varying the length of the track, etc).
1.4	TIME LAPSE	In the current real-life system steady state temperatures are achieved within a minute, so the time lapse of the analysis will be several minutes. The analysis will be conducted until steady state thermal conditions are reached.
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	The analysis will cover a printed heater track of several different geometries, with a constant DC current (TBC) being passed through it. The thickness of the printed tracks will be representative of realistic achievable film thicknesses (where thickness is governed by number of print passes, and therefore can only be defined in discrete steps).
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	N/A

2 GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION		
2.1	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Continuum coupled thermal-electrical analysis
2.2	MODEL ENTITY	The entity in this materials model is finite volumes.
2.3	MODEL PHYSICS/CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	<p>Equation</p> <p>The electric field in a conducting material is governed by Maxwell's equation of conservation of charge. Assuming steady-state direct current, the equation is equivalent to:</p> $\int_V \frac{\partial \delta \varphi}{\partial x} \cdot -\sigma^E \cdot \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x} dV = \int_S \delta \varphi J dS + \int_V \delta \varphi r_c dV$ <p>Flow of current is described by Ohm's law:</p> $\mathbf{J} = \sigma^E \cdot \mathbf{E} = -\sigma^E \cdot \frac{\partial \varphi}{\partial x}$ <p>where</p> <p>E is the electrical field intensity, defined as the negative of the gradient of the electrical potential ($\partial \varphi / \partial x$)</p> <p>$\varphi$ is the electrical potential,</p> <p>σ^E is the electrical conductivity matrix. When electrical conductivity depends on temperature (as in this case), the coupled problem is nonlinear.</p>
		<p>Physical quantities</p> <p>V is any control volume whose surface is S,</p> <p>\mathbf{n} is the outward normal to S,</p> <p>\mathbf{J} is the electrical current density (current per unit area),</p> <p>r_c is the internal volumetric current source per unit volume</p> <p>$\mathbf{J} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} -\mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{n}$ is the current density entering the control volume across S.</p>
2.4	MATERIALS	<p>Relation</p> <p>Joules Law describes rate of electrical energy dissipated by a current through a</p>

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	RELATIONS		conductor: $P_{cc} = \mathbf{J} \cdot \mathbf{E} = \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}^E \cdot \frac{\partial \phi}{\partial \mathbf{x}}$ The amount of this energy released as internal heat within the body is $\eta_v P_{cc}$
		Physical quantities/ descriptors for each MR	P_{cc} is the electrical energy dissipated by a current through a conductor η_v is an energy conversion factor. This is specified in the material definition. It is assumed that all the electrical energy is converted into heat ($\eta_v = 1.0$)
2.5	PHYSICS FORMULATION OF THE CONDITIONS	N/A	
2.6	SIMULATED INPUT	N/A	

3 SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS			
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Finite element	
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	Abaqus Standard	
3.3	TIME STEP	Estimated in 0.05s, to be reduced if convergence is difficult to attain in the nonlinear solution.	
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL	Coupled thermal-electrical analysis using exact Newton's method: $\begin{bmatrix} K_{\phi\phi} & K_{\phi\theta} \\ K_{\theta\phi} & K_{\theta\theta} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \Delta\phi \\ \Delta\theta \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{Bmatrix} R_\phi \\ R_\theta \end{Bmatrix}$ Where $\Delta\phi$ and $\Delta\theta$ respective corrections to the incremental electrical potential and temperature, K_{ij} are submatrices of the fully coupled Jacobian matrix, and R_ϕ and R_θ are the electrical and thermal residual vectors, respectively.
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	Constant DC current. No thermal emission to atmosphere by radiation, convection, or conduction. Temperature of "wires" at current inlet to be kept at room temperature.	
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	N/A	

4 POST PROCESSING			
4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	A surface plot will be generated with heat up rate/power required/amount of nanomaterial ink required for a number of different heater geometries. The most promising (i.e. highest temperature for lowest energy used) will be chosen as the input for Model 2. This will then be converted into a heat flux per unit area that will be applied to Model 3.	
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	<p>The following output variables will be requested from Abaqus:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> JENER - Electrical energy dissipated due to flow of current (element integration point variable) NT11 - (the reference temperature value) (element integration point variable) ELJD - Total electrical energy dissipated due to flow of current (whole element variable) ALLJD - Electrical energy summed over the model (whole model variable) SJD - Heat flux per unit area generated by the electrical current (surface interaction variable) ECD - Electrical current density (surface interaction variable) <p>The ALLJD variable will be compared for all the heater geometries to find the energy required to reach steady state conditions. The NT11 will be compared to find the maximum temperature of the geometry. These will be compared to find the overall most promising heater layout.</p>	
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	Sources of error in this analysis will be the assumption of no heat losses, the assumption of perfect conversion of electrical energy to heat energy within the system, and the assumption of bulk properties of the printed ink. The margin of error for these simulations are expected to be below 5%	

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Simulation with MODEL 2 – Heat conduction through composite

1 ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED		
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	This model will assess the heat up rate of the composite’s exterior face (with internally-mounted heaters), as well as identifying the ideal layout of heaters within an area to prevent local hot/cool spots.
1.2	MATERIAL	The wind turbine blade substrate identified in D7.1 will be used.
1.3	GEOMETRY	The heater geometry with the most promising configuration will be selected from the output of Model 1. The composite will be assessed over a 1m long piece of the wind turbine blade with the aerofoil shape defined in D7.1
1.4	TIME LAPSE	The analysis will be conducted until steady state thermal conditions are reached, which is expected to take minutes.
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	Blade average service temperature (as initial condition)
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	N/A

2 GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION		
2.1	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Continuum uncoupled heat transfer analysis
2.2	MODEL ENTITY	<i>Finite volumes</i>
2.3	MODEL PHYSICS/ CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	Equation The energy balance in a thermally conductive material is governed by the following equation: $\int_V \rho \dot{U} dV = \int_S q dS + \int_V r dV$
		Physical quantities V is any control volume of solid material whose surface is S, ρ is the density of the material, \dot{U} is the material time rate of the internal energy q is the heat flux per unit area of the body r _c is the heat supplied externally into the body per unit volume
2.4	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation Heat conduction is governed by the Fourier law: $\mathbf{f} = -\mathbf{k} \cdot \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \mathbf{x}}$
		Physical quantities/ descriptors for each MR k is the conductivity matrix f is the heat flux θ is the temperature, x is position
2.5	PHYSICS FORMULATION OF THE CONDITIONS	N/A
2.6	SIMULATED INPUT	The model will use the heat flux provided by the heater generated in Model 1 as an input. The heat up rate of the heater will also be used as part of the transient analysis.

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3 SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS		
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Finite element
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	Abaqus Standard
3.3	TIME STEP	Estimated in 0.05s, to be reduced if convergence is difficult to attain in the nonlinear solution.
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	<p>PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL</p> <p>Variational statement of the energy balance together with the Fourier law is obtained directly by the standard Galerkin approach</p> <p>First and second order polynomials as shape functions to interpolate the temperature from nodal values.</p> <p>Time integration - backward difference algorithm.</p>
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	<p>Initial temperature of the WTB section</p> <p>The boundary at the edge of the control volume will allow a constant heat flux out of the WTB section</p>
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	<p>Cavity radiation (within the aerofoil) will be included if it is shown to have a significant effect.</p> <p>No coupled thermal-stress analysis will be considered. Strains induced by the temperature change are out of scope.</p>

4 POST PROCESSING		
4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	<p>The following output variables will be requested from Abaqus:</p> <p>NT - Nodal point temperatures.</p> <p>HFL - Magnitude and components of the heat flux vector (element property).</p> <p>NFLUX - Fluxes at the nodes caused by heat conduction (internal fluxes).</p> <p>A surface plot of the temperature will be shown to identify hot/cold spots. Any area that is more than 10°C cooler than the average surface temperature will be identified as a problem and the layout of heaters adjusted to reduce this discrepancy</p>
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	The nodal point temperatures will be averaged and maximum/minimum temperatures will be found.
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	Sources of errors within this modelling step include the assumption that heat flux only passes out of the control volume, no radiation or convection heat transfer, and the assumption of perfect transference of heat flux from the printed heater. It is estimated that the margin of error will be less than 5%.

Simulation with MODEL 3 – Heating of blade with thermal emission to atmosphere

1 ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED		
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	This model will assess the heat up rate composite, taking into account the realistic in-service conditions to assess the power required to keep the WTB at service temperatures.
1.2	MATERIAL	The wind turbine blade substrate identified in D7.1 will be used.
1.3	GEOMETRY	<p>The heater geometry with the most promising configuration will be selected from the output of Model 2.</p> <p>The composite will be assessed over a 1m long piece of the wind turbine blade with the aerofoil shape defined in D7.1</p> <p>It is assumed that the WTB rotates too fast to have a significant effect on the temperature of the surrounding air. Therefore, a 10cm thick layer of fluid on the surface will be assessed.</p>

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1.4	TIME LAPSE	Minutes. The analysis will be conducted until steady state thermal conditions are reached.
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	Blade service temperature ranges The reference wind turbine blade is designed to operate at maximum 7.56 rpm (Table 22, D7.1) Assuming the control volume is halfway along the blades, the speed of rotation is 47.5 m/s.
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	N/A

2 GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION

2.1	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Continuum uncoupled heat transfer analysis	
2.2	MODEL ENTITY	Finite volumes	
2.3	MODEL PHYSICS/ CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	Equation	<p>The energy balance in a thermally conductive material is governed by the following equation:</p> $\int_V \rho \dot{U} dV = \int_S q dS + \int_V r dV$ <p>The energy balance in a continuum in which a fluid is flowing is governed by the following equation:</p> $\int_V d\theta \left[\rho c \left\{ \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial t} + \mathbf{v} \cdot \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right\} - \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \cdot \left(\mathbf{k} \cdot \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \mathbf{x}} \right) - q \right] dV + \int_{S_q} \partial \theta \left[\mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{k} \cdot \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \mathbf{x}} - q_s \right] dS = 0$
		Physical quantities	<p>V is any control volume of solid material whose surface is S, ρ is the density of the material, \dot{U} is the material time rate of the internal energy q is the heat flux per unit area of the body r_c is the heat supplied externally into the body per unit volume θ(x,t) is the temperature at a point, ∂θ(x, t) is an arbitrary variational field, P(θ) is the fluid density, C(θ) is the specific heat of the fluid, K(θ) is the conductivity of the fluid, q is the heat added per unit volume from external sources, q_s is the heat flowing into the volume across the surface on which temperature is not prescribed (S_n), n is the outward normal to the surface, x is spatial position, t is time.</p>
2.4	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation	<p>Heat conduction is governed by the Fourier law:</p> $\mathbf{f} = -\mathbf{k} \cdot \frac{\partial \theta}{\partial \mathbf{x}}$
		Physical quantities/ descriptors for each MR	<p>k is the conductivity matrix f is the heat flux θ is the temperature, x is position</p>

2.5	PHYSICS FORMULATION OF THE CONDITIONS	N/A
2.6	SIMULATED INPUT	The model will use the heat flux provided by the heater generated in Model 1 as an input. The heat up rate of the heater will also be used as part of the transient analysis. The layout of heaters in Model 2 will be used.

3 SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS

3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Finite element
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	Abaqus Standard
3.3	TIME STEP	Estimated in 0.05s, to be reduced if convergence is difficult to attain in the nonlinear solution.
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	<p>PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL</p> <p>Variational statement of the energy balance together with the Fourier law is obtained directly by the standard Galerkin approach</p> <p>First and second order polynomials as shape functions to interpolate the temperature from nodal values.</p> <p>Time integration - backward difference algorithm.</p>
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	<p>The boundary at the edge of the solid material in the control volume will allow a constant heat flux out of the WTB section.</p> <p>The temperature of the fluid at the external part of the control volume will be fixed at -20°C, to provide a worst case analysis.</p> <p>The speed of the fluid will be fixed at 47.5 m/s</p>
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	<p>Cavity radiation (within the aerofoil) will be included if it is shown to have a significant effect.</p> <p>No coupled thermal-stress analysis will be considered. Strains induced by the temperature change are out of scope.</p>

4 POST PROCESSING

4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	<p>The following output variables will be requested from Abaqus:</p> <p>NT - Nodal point temperatures.</p> <p>HFL - Magnitude and components of the heat flux vector (element property).</p> <p>NFLUX - Fluxes at the nodes caused by heat conduction (internal fluxes).</p> <p>A surface plot of the temperature will be shown to identify if the wind turbine blade can achieve an appropriate temperature when subjected to in-service conditions.</p>
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	The nodal point temperatures will be averaged and maximum/minimum temperatures will be found.
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	Sources of errors within this modelling step include the assumption that heat flux only passes out of the control volume, simplification of fluid flow during in-service conditions, and the assumption of perfect transference of heat flux from the printed heater. It is estimated that the margin of error will be less than 10%.

2.2 Modelling to support analysis of different CF treatments

MODA
MOdelling Data providing a description
for Modelling to support analysis of different CF treatments – Task 3.2.2
CARBO4POWER

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OVERVIEW of the SIMULATION								
1	USER CASE	The objective is to estimate relevant mechanical properties of continuous carbon fiber (CF) polymer matrix composite materials affected by different CF treatments. The purpose is obtaining the interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) and the mode II fracture toughness of the matrix/CF interphase through the simulation of push-out tests (inverse adjustment of the experimental tests). The properties obtained from the push-out models will feed micromechanics models of unidirectional fiber composites. The mechanical responses to be analysed will cover the elastic properties and the strengths (from the stress-strain curves in different material directions).						
2	CHAIN OF MODELS	<table border="1"> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">MODEL 1 - CONT</td> <td>CONTINUOUS MODEL of CFs push-out: Solid micromechanics model of the push-out of a carbon fiber embedded in a polymeric resin.</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">MODEL 2 - CONT</td> <td>CONTINUOUS MODEL of resin with unidirectional arrangements of fibers: Solid micromechanics model (solved with FE) of unidirectional arrangements of fibers over a RVE (description at μm-mm scale).</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">DATA MINING METHODOLOGY</td> <td>N/A</td> </tr> </table>	MODEL 1 - CONT	CONTINUOUS MODEL of CFs push-out: Solid micromechanics model of the push-out of a carbon fiber embedded in a polymeric resin.	MODEL 2 - CONT	CONTINUOUS MODEL of resin with unidirectional arrangements of fibers: Solid micromechanics model (solved with FE) of unidirectional arrangements of fibers over a RVE (description at μm - mm scale).	DATA MINING METHODOLOGY	N/A
		MODEL 1 - CONT	CONTINUOUS MODEL of CFs push-out: Solid micromechanics model of the push-out of a carbon fiber embedded in a polymeric resin.					
		MODEL 2 - CONT	CONTINUOUS MODEL of resin with unidirectional arrangements of fibers: Solid micromechanics model (solved with FE) of unidirectional arrangements of fibers over a RVE (description at μm - mm scale).					
DATA MINING METHODOLOGY	N/A							
PUBLICATION PEER-REVIEWING THE DATA	N/A							
4	ACCESS CONDITIONS	Available for CARBO4POWER partners or third parties under request.						
5	WORKFLOW AND ITS RATIONALE	The models will be used to estimate relevant mechanical properties of continuous CF polymer matrix composite materials. In addition, some specific properties of the resin/CF interphases will be determined.						

Figure 2.2 Workflow of Modelling to support analysis of different CF treatments – Task 3.2.2

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MODA

Modelling to support analysis of different CF treatments

Simulation with MODEL 1 – CONT: push-out tests

1		ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	Modelling the push-out test of a CF embedded in a resin matrix. This model will be used to determine the ILSS values and to estimate additional relevant parameters as the mode II interfacial fracture toughness. This will be done through an inverse experimental/numerical adjustment procedure.
1.2	MATERIAL	Carbon fiber / polymer matrix composites including the interphase between fibers-matrix.
1.3	GEOMETRY	<p>One CF within the polymeric matrix. The CF will have an interface cohesive surface around it. The specimen dimensions are approximately 80x80x25 μm. Nano-indenter similar to the one used in the experimental set-up. Specimen supported in similar way to the test.</p>
1.4	TIME LAPSE	Seconds (quasi-static analysis).
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	Pushing-out of the CF with the indenter.
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	N/A

2		GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION
2.1	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Continuum solid mechanics (micromechanics)
2.2	MODEL ENTITY	Finite elements
2.3	MODEL PHYSICS/CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	<p>Equation</p> <p>PE Conservation laws</p> <p>1. PE1. Mass conservation equation (continuity equation):</p> $\dot{\rho} + \rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0$ <p>2. PE2: Linear Momentum Balance</p> $\rho \dot{\mathbf{v}} - \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} - \rho \mathbf{b} = 0$ <p>3. PE3: Angular Momentum Balance</p> $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^T$ <p>4. PE4: Energy Balance</p>

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			$\rho \dot{e} - \sigma : (\nabla \mathbf{v}) + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} - \rho s = 0$
		Physical quantities	Physics quantities of PE1 to PE4: ρ is the mass density, \mathbf{v} is the velocity, σ is the Cauchy stress, \mathbf{b} is the body force per unit mass, e is the internal energy per unit mass, \mathbf{q} is the heat flux vector and s is the energy source per unit mass.
2.4	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation	1. MR1: Compatibility conditions $\nabla \times \mathbf{F} = \mathbf{0} \text{ finite strains}$ $\nabla \times (\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \mathbf{0} \text{ small strains}$ 2. MR2: Constitutive equations Additive decomposition of the strain rate $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{el} + \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{pl}$ Elasticity $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{D} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{el}$ Plasticity: Yield function, flow rule and hardening parameters evolution. $f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \theta, H_\alpha) = 0$ $d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{pl} = d\lambda \frac{\partial g(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \theta, H_\alpha)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ $dH_\alpha = d\lambda h_\alpha(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \theta, H_\alpha)$ Traction-separation laws for cohesive elements $\begin{cases} \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{K}' \boldsymbol{\delta} \text{ if } \boldsymbol{\sigma} < \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{crit} \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{K}' \boldsymbol{\delta} (1 - d) \text{ if } \boldsymbol{\sigma} > \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{crit} \end{cases}$
		Physical quantities/ descriptors for each MR	1. In MR1: \mathbf{F} is the deformation gradient, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the strain 2. In MR2: $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$ is the total strain rate, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{el}$ is the elastic strain rate, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{pl}$ is the plastic strain rate, \mathbf{D} is the stiffness tensor, f is the yield function, θ is the temperature, H_α are the hardening parameters, $d\lambda$ is the rate of change of plastic flow, g is the flow potential, h_α is the hardening law for H_α and $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ are the stress and strain respectively (for the last, differentiated between elastic and plastic). In addition, for the cohesive laws, $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ is the separation, \mathbf{K} is the penalty stiffness and d is the damage parameter.
2.5	PHYSICS FORMULATION OF THE CONDITIONS	N/A	
2.6	SIMULATED INPUT	N/A	

3	SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS		
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Continuum solid mechanics (micromechanics)	
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	Abaqus (http://www.3ds.com/es/productos-y-servicios/simulia)	
3.3	TIME STEP	Required for convergence of the Newton iterative method resolution of the non linear equations.	
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL	PE1+PE2 equilibrium equations are expressed in its weak form (virtual work principle). PE5: Virtual Work Principle $\int_V \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \delta \mathbf{D} dV = \int_S \delta \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{t} dS + \int_V \delta \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{f} dV$ $\mathbf{t} = \mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}$ Physics quantities of this PE5: \mathbf{D} is the strain rate, \mathbf{v} is the velocity, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress, \mathbf{f} is the body force per unit volume, \mathbf{t} is surface

		<p>traction per unit area.</p> <p>The equation PES is discretized and finally take the form of a set of algebraic equations in the form of:</p> $[K]\{q\} = \{F\}$ <p>Where $[K]$ is the system stiffness matrix, $\{q\}$ is the vector of nodal forces and $\{F\}$ is the vector of nodal forces.</p> <p>Material Relations: Incremental formulation is used for the elasto-plasticity.</p> <p>Material: The microstructure is discretized in a finite element mesh.</p> <p>The interfacial failure will be modelled through the utilization of cohesive elements.</p>
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	<p>Symmetry conditions in the two longitudinal planes of the CF.</p> <p>Specification of forces or displacements in nodes representing the load application in the experimental tests. Restriction in displacements in certain zones reproducing the specimen support / holding system.</p>
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	N/A

4	POST PROCESSING	
4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	Matrix-CF interface properties: interfacial shear strength and mode II fracture toughness.
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	<p>Interfacial shear strength estimated varying the maximum shear stress value defined in the cohesive elements formulation to adjust the experimental results.</p> <p>Fracture energies are computed from integration of force-displacement evolution</p>
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	Based on previous experiences, maximum error of around 25% is expected for these simulations.

Simulation with MODEL 2 - CONT: resin with UD arrangements

1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED	
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	This model addresses the simulation of a composite formed by unidirectional arrangements of fibers, incorporating the properties of their interface (obtained in Model 1), and obtaining the effective mechanical behaviour of the UD composite (elastic and strength). These properties will be analysed for materials with different CF treatments (standard or functionalised). The model will include the fiber/matrix debonding, which will depend on the functionalization effectiveness.
1.2	MATERIAL	Carbon fiber / polymer matrix composites including the interphase between fibers-matrix.
1.3	GEOMETRY	<p>Representative Volume Element (RVE) of Unidirectional arrangements of CFs within the polymeric homogenized matrix.</p>

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		The CFs will have an interphase layer around them or interface cohesive surface. RVE approx. dimensions: 150 μm x 80 μm x 80 μm (depending on the volumetric fraction of CF).
1.4	TIME LAPSE	Seconds (quasi-static analysis).
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	Periodic conditions: imposed deformation modes (three normal and three shear load modes).
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	N/A

2		GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION	
2.1	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Continuum solid mechanics (micromechanics)	
2.2	MODEL ENTITY	Finite elements	
2.3	MODEL PHYSICS/CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	Equation	PE Conservation laws 1. PE1: Mass conservation equation (continuity equation): $\dot{\rho} + \rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0$ 2. PE2: Linear Momentum Balance $\rho \dot{\mathbf{v}} - \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} - \rho \mathbf{b} = 0$ 3. PE3: Angular Momentum Balance $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^T$ 4. PE4: Energy Balance $\rho \dot{e} - \boldsymbol{\sigma} : (\nabla \mathbf{v}) + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} - \rho s = 0$
		Physical quantities	Physics quantities of PE1 to PE4: ρ is the mass density, \mathbf{v} is the velocity, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress, \mathbf{b} is the body force per unit mass, e is the internal energy per unit mass, \mathbf{q} is the heat flux vector and s is the energy source per unit mass.
2.4	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation	1. MR1: Compatibility conditions $\nabla \times \mathbf{F} = \mathbf{0}$ finite strains $\nabla \times (\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \mathbf{0}$ small strains 2. MR2: Constitutive equations Additive decomposition of the strain rate $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{el} + \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{pl}$ Elasticity $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{D} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{el}$ Plasticity: Yield function, flow rule and hardening parameters evolution. $f(\sigma, \theta, H_\alpha) = 0$ $d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{pl} = d\lambda \frac{\partial g(\sigma, \theta, H_\alpha)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ $dH_\alpha = d\lambda h_\alpha(\sigma, \theta, H_\alpha)$ Traction-separation laws for cohesive elements $\begin{cases} \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{K}' \boldsymbol{\delta} \text{ if } \sigma < \sigma_{crit} \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{K}' \boldsymbol{\delta} (1 - d) \text{ if } \sigma > \sigma_{crit} \end{cases}$

		Physical quantities/ descriptors each MR for	<p>1. In MR1: \mathbf{F} is the deformation gradient, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the strain</p> <p>2. In MR2: $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$ is the total strain rate, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{el}$ is the elastic strain rate, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{pl}$ is the plastic strain rate, \mathbf{D} is the stiffness tensor, f is the yield function, θ is the temperature, H_α are the hardening parameters, $d\lambda$ is the rate of change of plastic flow, g is the flow potential, h_α is the hardening law for H_α and σ and $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ are the stress and strain respectively (for the last, differentiated between elastic and plastic). In addition, for the cohesive laws, δ is the separation, K is the penalty stiffness and d is the damage parameter.</p>
2.5	PHYSICS FORMULATION OF THE CONDITIONS	N/A	
2.6	SIMULATED INPUT	Matrix-CF interface properties from Model 1.	

3 SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS

3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Finite Element Method (FEM)	
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	Abaqus (http://www.3ds.com/es/productos-y-servicios/simulia)	
3.3	TIME STEP	Required for convergence of the Newton iterative method resolution of the non linear equations.	
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	<p>PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL</p> <p>PE1+PE2 equilibrium equations are expressed in its weak form (virtual work principle).</p> <p>PE5: Virtual Work Principle</p> $\int_V \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \delta \mathbf{D} dV = \int_S \delta \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{t} dS + \int_V \delta \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{f} dV$ $\mathbf{t} = \mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}$ <p>Physics quantities of this PE5: \mathbf{D} is the strain rate, \mathbf{v} is the velocity, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress, \mathbf{f} is the body force per unit volume, \mathbf{t} is surface traction per unit area.</p> <p>The equation PE5 is discretized and finally take the form of a set of algebraic equations in the form of:</p> $[K]\{q\} = \{F\}$ <p>Where $[K]$ is the system stiffness matrix, $\{q\}$ is the vector of nodal forces and $\{F\}$ is the vector of nodal forces.</p> <p>Material Relations: Incremental formulation is used for the elasto-plasticity</p> <p>Material: The microstructure is discretized in a finite element mesh.</p> <p>The interfacial failure will be modelled through the utilization of cohesive elements.</p>	
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	Periodic boundary conditions. Different deformation modes (displacements imposed in different faces of the RVE).	
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	N/A	

4 POST PROCESSING

4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	Overall stress-strain curve of the composite representative of a UD composite.
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		Effective moduli. Strength properties.
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	Effective properties are calculated by volume averaging of the stress-strain fields or computation from the reaction forces obtained in the displacement constraints.
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	Based on previous experiences, maximum error of around 25% is expected for these simulations.

2.3 Simulation of infusion/RTM processes for TTB demonstrator

MODA
MOdelling Data providing a description
for Simulation of RTM process for TTB demonstrator – Task 3.2.3
CARBO4POWER

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OVERVIEW of the SIMULATION			
1	USER CASE	This model will give support to the design of the Resin Transfer Moulding (RTM) process proposed for one of the Tidal Turbine Blade (TTB) demos. The analysis will be carried out with the commercial simulation software Pam-RTM.	
2	CHAIN OF MODELS	MODEL 1	Continuum model – Fluid mechanics of the impregnation process during RTM for a specific product.
		DATA MINING METHODOLOGY	N/A
3	PUBLICATION PEER-REVIEWING THE DATA	N/A	
4	ACCESS CONDITIONS	Available for Carbo4Power partners and for third parties on demand.	
5	WORKFLOW AND ITS RATIONALE	The model is focused on the simulation of the RTM process that will be used for the manufacturing of one of the TTB demos, to check that an adequate impregnation/filling of the mould will be obtained and to optimize the amount and positions of the resin inlet and outlet points. The process being simulated is basically the resin flow while the reinforcement is being impregnated.	

Workflow picture

Figure 2.3 Workflow of Simulation of RTM process for TTB demonstrator – Task 3.2.3

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MODA

Physics-based Model

Simulation with MODEL 1

1 ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED		
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	RTM process for the TTB demo, based on the specifications of the manufacturer of the component and using the information that will be obtained from the experimental characterizations that will be performed during the project.
1.2	MATERIAL	Resin: 3R epoxy resin – specific formulation being developed in the project. Reinforcements: To be defined during the project execution. Generally TTB are manufactured combining glass and carbon fiber fabrics. Properties obtained from specific experimental characterizations that will be performed during the project.
1.3	GEOMETRY	Geometry of the TTB demo (still being defined)
1.4	TIME LAPSE	From minutes to few hours.
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	Processing temperatures (initial temperature of the resin, temperature of the mould/fabric), pressure at resin inlet points and resin flow rate. In addition, different inlet / outlet points distributions will be considered.
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	N/A

2 GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION		
2.1	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Continuum model – fluid mechanics. Incompressible, viscous flow through a porous medium (rheological model for the resin adjusted based on experimental tests, permeability properties of the reinforcements obtained from experimental characterizations). Optionally, heat transfer and chemical reaction can be included (cure kinetics models).
2.2	MODEL ENTITY	Finite volumes
2.3	MODEL PHYSICS/ CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	<p>Equation</p> <p>Continuity equation in the incompressible limit: $\nabla(V) = 0$</p> <p>Optionally heat transfer and curing can be also included: $\rho C_p \frac{dT}{dt} + \rho C_p \vec{V} \cdot \nabla T = \nabla[k \cdot \nabla T] + \rho w H \frac{d\alpha}{dt}$</p> <p>Heat balance equation considering curing kinetics and resin flow</p> <p>Physical quantities</p> <p>V = resin velocity P = density Cp = specific heat T = temperature t = time k = heat conductivity</p>

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			<p>w = resin mass fraction</p> <p>H = total heat generated during the reaction of the resin</p> <p>α = degree of cure</p>
2.4	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation	<p>Darcy's law:</p> $V = -\frac{K}{\mu}\nabla P$ <p>If heat transfer and curing are also considered, relations as the Kamal-Sourour model must be also considered:</p> $\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = (K_1 + K_2\alpha^m)(1 - \alpha)^n$ <p>In addition, the specific heat of the reinforcement (dry or wet) can be estimated as:</p> $\rho C_p = \varphi\rho_a C_{pa} + (1 - \varphi)\rho_f C_{pf}$ $k = \varphi k_a + (1 - \varphi)k_f$ $\rho C_p = \varphi\rho_r C_{pr} + (1 - \varphi)\rho_f C_{pf}$ $k = k_r + k_f$ <p>where 'a' stands for air, 'r' for resin and 'f' for fibre.</p> <p>Finally, the following material relations apply:</p> <p>$\mu = \mu(T, \alpha)$ - typically modified Arrhenius equations to include cure dependence.</p> <p>$K = K(\varphi)$ typically exponential, potential or Carman-Kozeny equation</p>
		Physical quantities/ descriptors for each MR	<p>V = resin velocity vector</p> <p>K = permeability tensor</p> <p>μ = viscosity</p> <p>P = pressure</p> <p>α = degree of cure</p> <p>t = time</p> <p>K_1, K_2 = reaction constants with an Arrhenius type of dependence with temperature</p> <p>m,n = reaction orders</p> <p>P = density</p> <p>Cp = specific heat</p> <p>k = heat conductivity</p> <p>φ = resin/air fraction</p>
2.5	PHYSICS FORMULATION OF THE CONDITIONS	N/A	
2.6	SIMULATED INPUT	N/A	

3 SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS		
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Finite element solver
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	Pam-RTM (ESI Group)
3.3	TIME STEP	Time step is automatically computed.
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	<p>PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL</p> <p>The flow is solved using a non-conforming finite element approximation. The pressure is discontinuous along the inter-elements boundaries except at the middle nodes. The pressure is interpolated using linear shape functions.</p> <p>The pressure is obtained from:</p> $[C]\{P\} = \{b\}$ <p>with</p> $[C] = \int [B]^T [E][B]dV$ <p>and</p> $[E] = \frac{1}{\phi\eta} \begin{bmatrix} Kx & Kxy \\ Kyx & Ky \end{bmatrix}$ $B_{ij} = \frac{\partial N_i}{\partial x_j}, \quad i=1,2 \text{ and } j=1,3$ <p>If heat transfer and curing are also considered, the heat generated by the reaction is introduced in the finite element formulation as a source. Time integration is performed with a predictor corrector schema.</p>
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	<p>Dirichlet conditions or imposed pressure (pressure specified on part of the boundary $d\Omega$):</p> $p = f(x, y, z)$ <p>If the injection is not assisted by vacuum, the pressure at the outlet points is the air pressure. At the inlet points the pressure is the one applied by the injection machine.</p> <p>Neumann conditions or imposed flow rate at the inlet points.</p> $V.n = Q$ <p>If heat transfer is considered, the temperature of the mould can be also established as a boundary condition.</p>
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	N/A

4 POST PROCESSING		
4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	The post-processing is based on a direct interpretation of the raw output (i.e. resin volume fraction at element level and cure degree).
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	The filling times and the best distribution of inlet/outlet points are determined based on the visual inspection of the resin filling history (for the different simulations performed with this model). The curing time is determined based on the cure degree evolution.
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	Based on previous experiences, a margin of error of about 15 % is expected.

2.4 Models for Bladelet tip design for WTB

MODA
MOdelling DAta providing a description
for Bladelet –tip Design for WTB - Task 3.3
CARBO4POWER

Thanasis Delizisis, BioG3D, adelizisis@biog3d.gr

OVERVIEW of the SIMULATION			
1	USER CASE	Bladelet tip for WTB will be simulated and designed in order to optimize its effectiveness by maximizing the output torque. More specifically, the bladelet will be designed for the Reference model of 15MW Offshore reference Wind Turbine, designed by NREL.	
2	CHAIN OF MODELS	MODEL 1	Continuum potential flow of 2D Simulation for bladelet airfoil.
		MODEL 2	Continuum CFD of WTB using RANS equations for optimization of Bladelet geometry
		MODEL 3	Continuum macro-mechanic: solid mechanics (conservation equations) to calculate structural dynamics.
		DATA MINING METHODOLOGY	N/A
3	PUBLICATION PEER-REVIEWING THE DATA	N/A	
4	ACCESS CONDITIONS	Available for Carbo4Power partners or third parties under request.	
5	WORKFLOW AND ITS RATIONALE	A Step by Step procedure proposed in order to determine the behaviour of the bladelet airfoil and WTB. This method is proposed due to time effective ratio. More specifically a starting point of simple and cost effective 2D potential flow analysis of the bladelet will give first results and will help to validate all the simulation parameters for CFD Analysis. Optimization Loop through CFD will help to design an aerodynamic effective bladelet. FEA will help to optimize the internal shape, by minimizing the weight of the final design.	

Workflow picture

Figure 2.4 Workflow of Bladelet –tip Design for WTB - Task 3.3

MODA

Physics-based Model

Simulation with MODEL 1-2D Analysis with Potential Flow for Wingtip Airfoil

1 ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED		
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	2D potential flow analysis will be simulated for the bladelet airfoil. In that step aerodynamic characteristics of wingtip will be defined through a variety of Angle of Attack
1.2	MATERIAL	The constituent materials are not relevant for this simulation
1.3	GEOMETRY	
1.4	TIME LAPSE	Steady State Simulation
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	Reynolds number=1E+7, AoA for a range from -10 up to 20deg
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	N/A

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2		GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION	
2.1	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Continuum model Fluid mechanics – Boundary element method (BEM) Potential Flow-Panel Method	
2.2	MODEL ENTITY	Boundary elements	
2.3	MODEL PHYSICS/ CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	Equation	Vorticity equation $\omega = \nabla u$ Bernoulli equation $\frac{1}{2}\rho \nabla u^2 + p = \text{constant}$
		Physical quantities	ρ : density \vec{u} : velocity vector ω : vorticity p : pressure
2.4	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation	N/A
		Physical quantities/ descriptors for each MR	N/A
2.5	PHYSICS FORMULATION OF THE CONDITIONS	N/A	
2.6	SIMULATED INPUT	N/A	

3		SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS	
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Boundary element method	
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	XFLR5	
3.3	TIME STEP	Steady state	
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL	Written up for the entity in the model.
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	Velocity Inlet Pressure Outlet No-Slip Wall	
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	N/A	

4	POST PROCESSING	
4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	The output (Lift to Drag ratio) allows to validate and choose appropriate turbulent model for 2D CFD Analysis of the wingtip airfoil in order to validate the results of model 2
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	N/A
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	N/A

MODEL 2-CFD Analysis of WTB-Bladelet Optimization Geometry

1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED	
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	CFD Analysis of WTB will be examined starting from 2D Analysis of bladelet FFA W3 211 airfoil. Result of CFD Simulation will be the shape optimization of WTB bladelet geometry.
1.2	MATERIAL	The constituent materials are not relevant for this simulation
1.3	GEOMETRY	
1.4	TIME LAPSE	Steady State Simulation
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	Reynolds number=1E+7, Using MRF a wind velocity of 10m/s will be examined
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	N/A

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2		GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION	
2.1	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Continuum model Fluid Mechanics Computation Fluid Dynamics (CFD) for determining Lift, Drag coefficients	
2.2	MODEL ENTITY	Finite Volumes	
2.3	MODEL PHYSICS/ CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	Equation	1 Navier-Stokes equations: Continuity equation $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} \nabla(\rho \vec{u}) = 0$ Momentum conservation equation $\rho \frac{\partial \vec{u}}{\partial t} + \nabla$ 2 k-ε model equations $\nabla(\rho u k) = \nabla \left(\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_k} \right) \nabla k \right) + G_k - \rho \varepsilon$ $\nabla(\rho u \varepsilon) = \nabla \left(\left(\mu + \frac{\mu_t}{\sigma_\varepsilon} \right) \nabla \varepsilon \right) + C_{1\varepsilon} \frac{\varepsilon}{k} G_k$
		Physical quantities	ρ: density \vec{u} : velocity vector t: time g: gravity acceleration μ: viscous stress tensor μ _t : Eddy viscosity k: Turbulent kinetic energy ε: Turbulent kinetic dissipation σ _k , G _k , C _{1ε} : Constants
2.4	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation	Newtonian fluid, viscous stress: $\tau = \mu \frac{\partial u}{\partial y}$ Turbulent viscosity $\mu_t = \rho C_\mu \frac{k^2}{\varepsilon}$
		Physical quantities/ descriptors for each MR	η: dynamic viscosity ρ: density τ: Shear Stress k: Turbulent kinetic energy ε: Turbulent kinetic dissipation C _μ : Constants
2.5	PHYSICS FORMULATION OF THE CONDITIONS	N/A	
2.6	SIMULATED INPUT	N/A	

3 SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS		
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Pressure-based finite volume
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	OpenFoam
3.3	TIME STEP	Steady state
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	<p>PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL</p> <p>1 equation for continuity, flux integration over the faces of a control volume (integral form replaced by summation of flux terms at each face)</p> <p>1 semi-discretized equation for momentum, applied to a control volume (Gaussian divergence theorem to replace the volume integrals over the control volume by surface integrals over the control surface)</p> <p>2 equations for turbulence model (k-ω SST)</p>
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	Velocity Inlet Pressure Outlet No-Slip Wall
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	N/A

4 POST PROCESSING		
4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	The output (Lift to Drag ratio) allows to determine the final stored torque of the WTB. Calculation of Torque allow to determine the effectiveness of the Bladelet Design.
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	<p>Different design approaches of the bladelet are compared. The result of that action is the selection of the most promising design, in order to proceed with shape optimization.</p> <p>Lift Coefficient</p> $C_L = \frac{1}{2} \frac{L}{\rho u^2 C}$ <p>Drag Coefficient</p> $C_D = \frac{1}{2} \frac{D}{\rho u^2 C}$ <p>Reynolds number</p> $\Re = \frac{\rho u C}{\mu}$ <p>ρ: density</p> <p>U: velocity vector</p> <p>μ: viscous stress tensor</p> <p>μ_t: Eddy viscosity</p> <p>C: Characteristic length</p> <p>Re: Reynolds number</p> <p>C_L, C_D: Lift and Drag Coefficients</p>
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	Based on previous experiences, maximum error of around 6% is expected.

MODEL 3- FEA Analysis of WTB

1 ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED		
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	In that step Structural dynamic response of Bladelet will be simulated. The prediction of the structural response of WT bladelet due to the aerodynamic forces and moments will lead to an optimization of internal geometry, minimizing the weight of the structure.
1.2	MATERIAL	Ultracur3D EPD 1006/2006 Commercial (BASF)
1.3	GEOMETRY	Optimal geometry of that in Model 2
1.4	TIME LAPSE	N/A Static analysis
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	Static load cases
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	N/A

2 GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION		
2.1	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Continuum solid mechanics model (macro-mechanics)
2.2	MODEL ENTITY	Finite elements
2.3	MODEL PHYSICS/ CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	<p style="text-align: right;">Equation</p> <p>PE Conservation laws. PE1. Mass conservation equation (continuity equation):</p> $\frac{\partial \rho'}{\partial t} + v'_j \frac{\partial \rho'}{\partial x_j} + \rho_0 \left(1 + \frac{\rho'}{\rho_0} \right) \frac{\partial v'_i}{\partial x_i} = 0$ <p>2. PE2: Linear Momentum Balance</p> $\frac{\partial \sigma_{ij}}{\partial y_i} + \rho b_j = \rho \alpha_j$ <p>3. PE3: Angular Momentum Balance</p> $\int_A \sigma_{ji} n_j dA + \int_V \rho b_i dV = \frac{d}{dt} \left\{ \int_V \rho v_i dV \right\}$ <p style="text-align: right;">Physical quantities</p> <p>Physics quantities of PE1 to PE4: ρ is the mass density, v is the velocity, σ is the Cauchy stress, b is the body force per unit mass, e is the internal energy per unit mass, q is the heat flux vector and s is the energy source per unit mass.</p>
2.4	MATERIALS RELATIONS	<p style="text-align: right;">Relation</p> <p>1. MR1: Compatibility conditions finite strains $\epsilon = \frac{\Delta L}{L_0}$ Normal strain</p> <p>2. MR2: Constitutive equations Additive decomposition of the strain rate $\dot{\epsilon} = \dot{\epsilon}^{el} + \dot{\epsilon}^p$</p> <p style="text-align: right;">Physical quantities/ descriptors for each MR</p> <p>1. In MR1: F is the deformation gradient, ϵ is the strain</p> <p>2. In MR2: $\dot{\epsilon}$ is the total strain rate, $\dot{\epsilon}^{el}$ is the elastic strain rate, $\dot{\epsilon}^{pl}$ is the plastic strain rate, D is the stiffness tensor, f is the yield function, θ is the temperature, H_α are the hardening parameters, $d\lambda$ is the rate of change of plastic flow, g is the flow potential, h_α is the hardening law for H_α and σ and</p>

			ε are the stress and strain respectively (for the last, differentiated between elastic and plastic).
2.5	PHYSICS FORMULATION OF THE CONDITIONS	N/A	
2.6	SIMULATED INPUT	Pressure distribution from Model 2	

3 SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS			
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Implicit FE method	
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	TBD	
3.3	TIME STEP	Steady state Static	
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	<p>PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL</p> <p>PE1+PE2 equilibrium equations are expressed in its weak form (virtual work principle).</p> <p>PE5: Virtual Work Principle</p> $\int \delta \varepsilon \tau A dx \int f \delta u dx + R \delta u _{x=L}$ <p>Physics quantities of this PE5: D is the strain rate, v is the velocity, σ is the Cauchy stress, f is the body force per unit volume, t is surface traction per unit area.</p> <p>The equation PE5 is discretized and finally take the form of a set of algebraic equations in the form of:</p> $[K]\{u\} = \{F\}$ <p>Where $[K]$ is the system stiffness matrix, $\{u\}$ is the column matrix (vertex) of nodal forces and $\{F\}$ is the vector of nodal forces.</p> <p>Material: The microstructure is discretized in a finite element mesh.</p>	
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	Root is Fixed, Loads are imported from Model 2	
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	N/A	

4 POST PROCESSING			
4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	The calculated results are imported for visualizing the a) stressed areas and displacements. Identification of critical areas based on a failure criterion. Determination of safety factors. Bladelet efficiency	
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	TBD. Depending on the failure criterion, analysis in terms of stresses/strains or calculation or expression for more complex criteria.	
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	Based on previous experiences, maximum error of around X5% is expected.	

2.5 Modelling coatings and their effects in WTB/TTB performance

MODA
MOdelling Data providing a description
for Modelling coatings and their effects in WTB/TTB performance - Task 3.4
CARBO4POWER

Dr. Andreas Flanschger, bionic surface technologies, flanschger@bionicsurface.com

OVERVIEW of the SIMULATION			
1	USER CASE	The aim of the simulation model is to see the change of flow around a wind- or tidal turbine blade due to coatings and surface structures. In order not to completely resolve the flow around surface structures and coatings in the nano- to micrometer range, a model is used to simulate flows in a bigger scale.	
2	CHAIN OF MODELS	MODEL 1	3D CFD turbulence model with smooth surface
		MODEL 2	3D CFD turbulence model with coatings
3	PUBLICATION PEER-REVIEWING THE DATA	N/A	
4	ACCESS CONDITIONS	To be defined	
5	WORKFLOW AND ITS RATIONALE	Special surface structures and coatings such as Riblets have dimensions in micrometer scale; this means that a CFD simulation of such structures is only possible at a very small domain or with an extremely high computational effort. To overcome this problem Bionic Surface Technologies GmbH (BST) developed an algorithm which accounts for the influence of the coatings at simulations with a bigger scale like wind turbine blades.	

Model 1: smooth surface

Model 2: surface structures

Figure 2.5 Workflow of Modelling coatings and their effects in WTB/TTB performance - Task 3.4

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MODA

Physics-based Model

MODEL 1: 3D CFD turbulence model with smooth surface

1 ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED		
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	<p>Model 1 is a 3D CFD (computational fluid dynamics) simulation of the wind turbine blades (WTB) and tidal turbine blades (TTB) with a smooth surface. These simulations serve as the basis for the subsequent simulations with applied coatings such as Riblets.</p> <p>The flow field (magnitude and direction of velocity, wall-shear, pressure, etc.) will be used to design the surface structures (e.g. Riblets) for Model 2. In addition lift, drag and the resulting aerodynamic performance of the WTB and TTB will be used to evaluate the difference in aerodynamic performance between smooth surface and surfaces with coatings.</p>
1.2	MATERIAL	The volume zone consists of air (WTB) and water (TTB). The material of the WTB and TTB is not relevant for this simulation.
1.3	GEOMETRY	Geometry of the WTB and TTB.
1.4	TIME LAPSE	N/A (steady simulation)
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	<p>The boundary conditions are a velocity inlet (wind speed at WTB; water flow speed at TTB) and a pressure outlet with ambient pressure.</p> <p>The domain including the WTB/TTB will be set as MRF (Multiple Reference Frame) to account for the rotation.</p> <p>The walls are modeled as non-slip smooth surfaces.</p> <p>Periodicities are to be included when a single blade is simulated.</p>
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	N/A

2 GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION		
2.1	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Continuum model – Computational Fluid Dynamics
2.2	MODEL ENTITY	Finite volumes 3D
2.3	MODEL PHYSICS/CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	<p style="text-align: center;">Equation</p> <p>Navier-Stokes equations Continuity equation:</p> $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0$ <p>Equation for momentum conservation:</p> $\frac{\partial \rho \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}) = \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} + \rho \mathbf{f}^b$ <p>Transport equations for the Shear-Stress Transport (SST) k-ω model. This model is using the eddy viscosity approach according to Boussinesq to overcome the closure problem in turbulence.</p> $\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho k) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} (\rho k u_i) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\Gamma_k \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right) + G_k - Y_k + S_k$ <p>and</p> $\frac{\partial}{\partial t} (\rho \omega) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} (\rho \omega u_j) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\Gamma_\omega \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_j} \right) + G_\omega - Y_\omega + D_\omega + S_\omega$

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		Physical quantities	<p>ρ: density</p> <p>t: time</p> <p>\mathbf{u}: velocity vector</p> <p>$\underline{\sigma}$: Tensor of pressure and viscous forces</p> <p>\mathbf{f}^b: vector of volume forces</p> <p>k: turbulent kinetic energy</p> <p>ω: specific dissipation</p> <p>$x_{i,j}$: coordinate directions</p> <p>Γ_k: diffusivity of turbulent kinetic energy k</p> <p>Γ_ω: diffusivity of specific dissipation ω</p> <p>G_k: production of turbulent kinetic energy k</p> <p>G_ω: production of specific dissipation ω</p> <p>Y_k: dissipation of turbulent kinetic energy k</p> <p>Y_ω: dissipation of specific dissipation ω</p> <p>D_ω: cross-diffusion term</p> <p>$S_{k,\omega}$: user-defined source terms</p>
2.4	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation	Values of air and water will come from literature and partners.
		Physical quantities/ descriptors for each MR	<p>τ: shear stress</p> <p>η: dynamic viscosity</p> <p>$\dot{\gamma}$: shear rate</p>
2.5	PHYSICS FORMULATION OF THE CONDITIONS	Newtonian fluid:	$\tau = \eta * \dot{\gamma}$
2.6	SIMULATED INPUT	N/A	

3 SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS		
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Pressure-based finite volume solver
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	ANSYS Fluent (commercial application)
3.3	TIME STEP	Steady simulation
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	<p>PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL</p> <p>1 equation for continuity, flux integration over the faces of a control volume (integral form replaced by summation of flux terms at each face)</p> <p>1 semi-discretized equation for momentum, applied to a control volume (Gaussian divergence theorem to replace the volume integrals over the control volume by surface integrals over the control surface)</p> <p>2 equations for turbulence model (k-ω SST)</p> <p>Energy equation is not considered since the mach-number Ma is below 0.3 (incompressible fluid).</p> <p>Radiation is not considered.</p>
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	Velocity inlet, pressure outlet, periodicity conditions and walls.

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3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	N/A
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4 POST PROCESSING		
4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	<p>One output of this model is the flow field in the boundary layer close to the walls. These values together with the Bionic Surface Technologies GmbH (BST) algorithm will be used to create a certain slip velocity which models the effects of surface structures for model 2.</p> <p>Another important output is the aerodynamic performance, which is used to examine the difference between cases with smooth surfaces and surfaces with coatings like Riblets. The aerodynamic performance is made up of the lift coefficient and drag coefficient of the WTB or TTB.</p>
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	<p>Lift coefficient : $C_L = \frac{F_L}{\frac{\rho}{2} v^2 \cdot A}$</p> <p>Drag coefficient: $C_D = \frac{F_D}{\frac{\rho}{2} v^2 \cdot A}$</p> <p>Calculation of lift and drag force: $F_{L,D} = \int p \cdot dA$</p> <p>Aerodynamic performance: $C_{eff} = \frac{C_L}{C_D}$</p> <p>$F_L$: Lift force [N] F_D: Drag force [N] v: velocity [m/s] A: Relevant surface area [m²] p: pressure [Pa]</p>
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	Based on previous experiences, maximum error of around 5% is expected.

MODEL 2: 3D CFD turbulence model with coatings

1 ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED		
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	<p>Model 2 is a 3D CFD (computational fluid dynamics) simulation of the wind turbine blades (WTB) and tidal turbine blades (TTB) with applied surface structures such as Riblets.</p> <p>Lift, drag and the resulting aerodynamic performance of the WTB and TTB will be used to evaluate the difference in aerodynamic performance between smooth surface and surfaces with coatings.</p>
1.2	MATERIAL	<p>The volume zone consists of air (WTB) and water (TTB).</p> <p>The material of the WTB and TTB is not relevant for this simulation.</p>
1.3	GEOMETRY	Geometry of the WTB and TTB.
1.4	TIME LAPSE	N/A (steady simulation)
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	<p>The boundary conditions are a velocity inlet (wind speed at WTB; water flow speed at TTB) and a pressure outlet with ambient pressure.</p> <p>The domain including the WTB/TTB will be set as MRF (Multiple Reference Frame) to account for the rotation.</p> <p>The walls are modelled with a certain slip velocity.</p> <p>Periodicities are to be included when a single blade is simulated.</p>
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	N/A

2		GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION	
2.1	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Continuum model – Computational Fluid Dynamics	
2.2	MODEL ENTITY	Finite volumes 3D	
2.3	MODEL PHYSICS/ CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	Equation	<p>Navier-Stokes equations</p> <p>Continuity equation:</p> $\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0$ <p>Equation for momentum conservation:</p> $\frac{\partial \rho \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u}) = \nabla \cdot \underline{\underline{\sigma}} + \rho \mathbf{f}^b$ <p>Transport equations for the Shear-Stress Transport (SST) k-ω model. This model is using the eddy viscosity approach according to Boussinesq to overcome the closure problem in turbulence.</p> $\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho k) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i}(\rho k u_i) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\Gamma_k \frac{\partial k}{\partial x_j} \right) + G_k - Y_k + S_k$ <p>and</p> $\frac{\partial}{\partial t}(\rho \omega) + \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j}(\rho \omega u_j) = \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} \left(\Gamma_\omega \frac{\partial \omega}{\partial x_j} \right) + G_\omega - Y_\omega + D_\omega + S_\omega$
		Physical quantities	<p>ρ: density</p> <p>t: time</p> <p>\mathbf{u}: velocity vector</p> <p>$\underline{\underline{\sigma}}$: Tensor of pressure and viscous forces</p> <p>\mathbf{f}^b: vector of volume forces</p> <p>k: turbulent kinetic energy</p> <p>ω: specific dissipation</p> <p>x_{ij}: coordinate directions</p> <p>Γ_k: diffusivity of turbulent kinetic energy k</p> <p>Γ_ω: diffusivity of specific dissipation ω</p> <p>G_k: production of turbulent kinetic energy k</p> <p>G_ω: production of specific dissipation ω</p> <p>Y_k: dissipation of turbulent kinetic energy k</p> <p>Y_ω: dissipation of specific dissipation ω</p> <p>D_ω: cross-diffusion term</p> <p>$S_{k,\omega}$: user-defined source terms</p>
2.4	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation	Values of air and water will come from literature and partners.
		Physical quantities/ descriptors for each MR	<p>τ: shear stress</p> <p>η: dynamic viscosity</p> <p>$\dot{\gamma}$: shear rate</p>
2.5	PHYSICS FORMULATION OF THE CONDITIONS	Newtonian fluid:	$\tau = \eta * \dot{\gamma}$
2.6	SIMULATED INPUT	The flow field of model 1 in the boundary layer close to the walls is taken as input for this simulation. Together with the BST algorithm a certain slip velocity is created at areas where	

		surface structures should be applied. This approach is modelling the effect of such surface structures on the flow field.
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3 SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS		
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Pressure-based finite volumes solver
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	ANSYS Fluent (commercial application)
3.3	TIME STEP	Steady simulation
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	<p>PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL</p> <p>1 equation for continuity, flux integration over the faces of a control volume (integral form replaced by summation of flux terms at each face)</p> <p>1 semi-discretized equation for momentum, applied to a control volume (Gaussian divergence theorem to replace the volume integrals over the control volume by surface integrals over the control surface)</p> <p>2 equations for turbulence model (k-ω SST)</p> <p>Energy equation is not considered since the mach-number Ma is below 0.3 (incompressible fluid).</p> <p>Radiation is not considered.</p>
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	Velocity inlet, pressure outlet, periodicity conditions and walls.
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	N/A

4 POST PROCESSING		
4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	The output is the aerodynamic performance, which is used to examine the difference between cases with smooth surfaces and surfaces with coatings like Riblets. The aerodynamic performance is made up of the lift coefficient and drag coefficient of the WTB or TTB.
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	<p>Lift coefficient : $C_L = \frac{F_L}{\frac{\rho}{2} v^2 \cdot A}$</p> <p>Drag coefficient: $C_D = \frac{F_D}{\frac{\rho}{2} v^2 \cdot A}$</p> <p>Calculation of lift and drag force: $F_{L,D} = \int p \cdot dA$</p> <p>Aerodynamic performance: $c_{eff} = \frac{C_L}{C_D}$</p> <p>$F_L$: Lift force [N]</p> <p>$F_D$: Drag force [N]</p> <p>v: velocity [m/s]</p> <p>A: Relevant surface area [m²]</p> <p>p: pressure [Pa]</p>
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	Based on previous experiences, maximum error of around 5% is expected.

2.6 Models for Design and analysis of WTB

MODA
MOdelling DAta providing a description
for Blade Structural Simulation Model - Task 3.5
CARBO4POWER

Peter Greaves – ORE Catapult – peter.greaves@ore.catapult.org.uk

OVERVIEW of the SIMULATION			
1	USER CASE	The goal is to assess the structural performance of wind turbine blades (WTB) against the requirements laid down in the design standards. The focus is to assess different failure criteria such as fibre failure, inter-fibre failure, core material failure, fatigue failure and bond line failure and ensure that the blade can pass these cases with partial safety factors applied.	
2	CHAIN OF MODELS	MODEL 1	CONTINUUM. Aero-elastic simulations of wind turbine behaviour to obtain design loads which can be applied to the finite element model of the blade.
		MODEL 2	CONTINUUM. Finite element model to which the loads obtained from Model 1 are applied.
		DATA MINING METHODOLOGY	N/A
3	PUBLICATION REVIEWING THE DATA	W Collier and J Milian Sanz Comparison of linear and non-linear blade model predictions in Bladed to measurement data from GE 6MW wind turbine 2016 J. Phys.: Conf. Ser. 753 082004	
4	ACCESS CONDITIONS	Model 1 – Bladed Model of the IEA 15MW reference turbine – freely available (Bladed is commercial software) Model 2 – ANSYS APDL input deck – freely available (ANSYS is commercial software)	
5	WORKFLOW AND ITS RATIONALE	The use of aero-elastic software to generate load time histories is the usual method for the wind industry and well described by standards. Bladed is considered to be the industry standard software for this purpose. Once loads have been obtained they are processed to find their extreme values and equivalent fatigue loads and these loads are applied to a finite element model of the blade developed in a commercial software.	

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Figure 2.6 Workflow for Blade Structural Simulation Model – Task 3.5

Elements in the Simulation of Model 1 – CONT: Aero-elastic simulations of design load cases

1 ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED		
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	Evaluation of the design loads for the reference blade.
1.2	MATERIAL	NA – the blade and tower are reduced to a beam model with stiffness properties which are a result of both the material stiffness properties and the cross-section geometry of the blade.
1.3	GEOMETRY	<p>Geometry of the reference Wind Turbine</p> <p>The turbine is represented using beam finite elements – the below picture is a visual rendering.</p>

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1.4	TIME LAPSE	The duration of individual simulations varies depending on which load case is being simulated, but typically 1000+ simulations of around 600s are performed to capture the full range of operational conditions for the turbine.
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DLC 1.1 - Power production in normal turbulence (ultimate - extreme extrapolation) • DLC 1.2 - Power production in normal turbulence (fatigue) • DLC 1.3 - Power production in extreme turbulence (ultimate) • DLC 1.4 - Power production in extreme coherent gust with wind direction change (ultimate) • DLC 1.5 - Power production in extreme wind shear (ultimate) • DLC 6.1 - Parked in 50-year extreme wind (ultimate) • DLC 6.4 – Parked (fatigue)
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	W Collier and J Milian Sanz Comparison of linear and non-linear blade model predictions in Bladed to measurement data from GE 6MW wind turbine 2016 J. Phys.: Conf. Ser. 753 082004

2 GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION		
2.1	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Continuum - Structural Dynamics Wind turbine simulation codes aim to capture many different effects in one simulation code. These effects include: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Aerodynamic loading (blade element momentum theory with corrections)

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		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Turbulent wind models (Mann, Von Karman) • Structural dynamics (nonlinear beam finite-elements for the blades, tower and foundation) • Hydrodynamic loading (Morison's equation) • Servo loading (pitch and yaw actuation, generator loads etc) • Electrical dynamics
2.2	MODEL ENTITY	The entities in this model are beam finite elements
2.3	MODEL PHYSICS/CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	Equation <p>The structural dynamics equation is solved in modal space to find the state accelerations:</p> $M\ddot{q} + C\dot{q} + Kq = f$ <p>In addition, Bladed implements many equations describing multiple different physics as described (but not limited to) the examples in section 2.1.</p> <p>These equations are described in the Bladed theory manual which is available on request from ORE Catapult.</p>
		Physical quantities <p>M, C, and K are the system modal matrices for mass, damping and stiffness respectively q, \dot{q}, \ddot{q} and are the state displacements, velocities and accelerations respectively f is the modal vector of externally applied forces on each state</p>
2.4	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation <p>Multi-member modal approach - flexible components are linear space beams or more general space frames that comprise assemblies of multiple members modelled by Timoshenko beam elements</p>
		Physical quantities/descriptors for each MR <p>N/A</p>
2.5	PHYSICS FORMULATION OF THE CONDITIONS	Ref. Models mentioned in section 2.1
2.6	SIMULATED INPUT	N/A

3	SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS	
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Runge-Kutta 4 th /5 th Order with variable time step
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	DNV-GL Blade
3.3	TIME STEP	Variable 1e-7s to 1s – typically 0.05s
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL <p>The calculation procedure used by Bladed can be represented as follows:</p>

			<p>More details can be found in Bladed theory manual.</p>
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	Tower base is considered as rigidly fixed. Initial rotor speed is set to what it should be for the mean wind speed. First 20s of simulation are discarded to allow initial transients to decay.	
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time integrator - Runge-Kutta 4/5th order (variable step) • Time step limits – Min: 1e-7s Max: 1s • Integrator relative tolerance 0.005 	

4 POST PROCESSING

4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	<p>Ultimate Load Cases</p> <p>The processed output is an envelope of the extreme loads at each section along the blade (see section 1.3 first figure). The output from the aero-elastic tool is time histories of the beam loads (axial force F_z, shear forces F_x and F_y, bending moments M_x and M_y and torsional moment M_z) for each load case.</p> <p>As there are many hundreds of load cases, each around 600s long, they need to be processed to find the most extreme conditions. The response of the blade is dominated by the bending moments M_x and M_y so this process is aimed at matching the extremes of these quantities as closely as possible.</p> <p>The red dots in the below figure represent a point in the time histories. Time histories for all load cases will be concatenated together and then each point will be projected onto a vector at 30° intervals, with the most extreme points taken. This extreme point is then presented in a tabular format as described in DNV-GL ST0376.</p>
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This leads to an envelope of bending loads for each section of blade as shown in the figure

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below (each different coloured line represents a section from along the blade, with the outermost being the blade root).

Fatigue Load Cases

For fatigue load cases, the time history of forces is reduced using damage equivalent loads. After rainflow counting of all load time histories concatenated together and adjusted for the predicted number of occurrences the equivalent load is calculated as below, where m is the slope of the SN curve, n_i is the number of occurrences for cycle i , F_i is the load amplitude for cycle i and n_{DEL} is the number of cycles for which the design equivalent load is being calculated (for example 10^6).

$$F_{equivalent} = \left(\frac{n_{DEL}}{\sum \frac{n_i}{(F_i)^m}} \right)^{-m}$$

For both fatigue and ultimate cases, the output of this process will be a bending moment distribution. We must then calculate a distributed shear force distribution which would reproduce this bending moment distribution as shown below. This is accomplished using an optimisation routine. These loads are then suitable for applying to an FE model in the next step in the model chain.

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4.2	METHODOLOGIES	For the ultimate cases, the vector of each individual time history data point (the blue line in the first figure above) is projected onto the load resolution vector (the red line in the figure above). The black arrow is the vector projection, and the largest positive value of the magnitude of this vector is chosen to be the envelope position for a given load resolution angle. For the fatigue load cases, the same approach is used except the full time history is retained and rainflow counted before a damage equivalent load calculation is applied as above.
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	The margin of error is unknown because we are calculating loads for a notional wind field which is impossible to reproduce in practice. For this reason, partial safety factors are applied to all loads and material properties to ensure a safe design is achieved. For ultimate load cases the safety factor for loads is typically 1.35 which accounts for any inaccuracies in the simulation or errors which can be incurred by postprocessing the data to reduce the required volume of analysis.

Elements in the Simulation of Model 2 – CONT: Finite Element Model of the reference blade

1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED	
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	Evaluation of failure criteria for the reference blade under design loads.
1.2	MATERIAL	The materials are the Carbo4Power reference materials described in Deliverable 7.1. They are described as orthotropic materials.
1.3	GEOMETRY	Geometry of the WTB
1.4	TIME LAPSE	N/A for static and modal analyses.
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	The blade root is constrained to have zero displacement. The shear force distribution described in Model 1 section 4.1 is applied to the nodes representing the spar cap.
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	N/A

2	GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION					
2.1	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Continuum – Structural Mechanics				
2.2	MODEL ENTITY	<i>The entities in this model are finite elements</i>				
2.3	MODEL PHYSICS/CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	<table border="0" style="width: 100%;"> <tr> <td style="width: 50%;">Equation</td> <td>Static Analysis</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td>The equations for a static analysis are as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The derivation of the structural matrices are described here in section 2.2. Obtaining solution stresses and strains is described here The solution of a static problem is described here in section 15.1 For a nonlinear static solution the procedure is described here </td> </tr> </table>	Equation	Static Analysis		The equations for a static analysis are as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The derivation of the structural matrices are described here in section 2.2. Obtaining solution stresses and strains is described here The solution of a static problem is described here in section 15.1 For a nonlinear static solution the procedure is described here
Equation	Static Analysis					
	The equations for a static analysis are as follows: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> The derivation of the structural matrices are described here in section 2.2. Obtaining solution stresses and strains is described here The solution of a static problem is described here in section 15.1 For a nonlinear static solution the procedure is described here 					

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			<p>Eigenbuckling Analysis</p> <p>The equation being solved for an eigenbuckling problem is described here. The stress-stiffening matrix is described here.</p>
		Physical quantities	Physical quantities and relations are described on the above pages.
2.4	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation	Relationships between stress and strain are described here in section 2.1.
		Physical quantities/ descriptors for each MR	Physical quantities and relations are described in the link indicated above.
2.5	PHYSICS FORMULATION OF THE CONDITIONS	N/A	
2.6	SIMULATED INPUT	Simulated input is obtained from post-processed aero-elastic simulations as described in model 1 – section 4.1.	

3 SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS

3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Static Solver/Nonlinear static solver/Eigenbuckling solver	
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	ANSYS APDL	
3.3	TIME STEP	NA, but nonlinear loads typically started with 10 substeps and automatic step length turned on.	
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	<p>PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL</p>	<p>See ANSYS theory manual links in section 2.3.</p> <p>The blade is represented using shell and solid finite elements – the below picture is a visual rendering of the magnitude of the displacement for an extreme load case.</p> <p>The element connectivity, nodal coordinates and section data are calculated by direct meshing with ORE Catapult’s in-house mesh generation tool.</p>
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL	The blade root is constrained to have zero displacement. The shear force distribution	

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	BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	described in Model 1 section 4.1 is applied to the nodes representing the spar cap. For an eigenbuckling analysis a static case is run first with the option to output a stress stiffening matrix then the eigenbuckling simulation is performed.
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	30 buckling modes are extracted.

4 POST PROCESSING

4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	<p>Failure Criteria</p> <p>The Puck failure criteria is used as prescribed by DNV-GL ST0376 and IEC 61400-5.</p>
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	METHODOLOGIES	<p>The following procedure is followed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Variables relating to the Puck failure criterion are created Loop to find maximum number of layers used in the model Loop over layers <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Loop over elements and apply equations below If layer has higher failure index than any seen previously in this element save the result for this element and save the layer which failed for this element. <p>Puck failure theory applies to unidirectional fibers. There are two different Puck failure criteria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fiber failure criterion — In this criterion, two mutually exclusive fiber failure criteria equations are developed. One equation is used if fibers fail under tension and the other equation is used if fibers fail under compression. Matrix failure criterion — In this criterion, three mutually exclusive matrix failure criteria equations are developed. They are called: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> Inter-fiber failure mode A Inter-fiber failure mode B Inter-fiber failure mode C
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4.2		<p style="text-align: center;">Matrix failure modes</p>
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		<p>The Puck failure theory needs the following empirical material properties:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Inclination parameter (+) on the tension side, $P_{\perp }^+$. This parameter sets the slope of the fracture envelope at zero normal transverse stress, on the tension side. Inclination parameter (-) on the compression side, $P_{\perp }^-$. This parameter sets the slope of the fracture envelope at zero normal transverse stress, on the compression side.
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These are empirical material properties and their value must be found experimentally. The following table summarizes the recommended values for these properties for two typical fiber reinforced polymers with 60% fiber volume fraction [6].

	$P_{\perp }^+$	$P_{\perp }^-$
Glass fiber / epoxy	0.3	0.25
Carbon fiber / epoxy	0.35	0.3

Fiber failure under tension

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		$F_f = \frac{\epsilon_1}{X_{T\epsilon}} \leq 1$ <p>Where $X_{T\epsilon}$ is the tensile strain allowable in direction 1 of the unidirectional ply (the second term inside the brackets is ignored).</p> <p>Fiber failure under compression</p> <p>The expression for the fiber failure index, F_f is:</p> $F_f = \frac{ \epsilon_1 }{X_{C\epsilon}} \leq 1$ <p>where $X_{C\epsilon}$ is the compressive strain allowable in direction 1 of the unidirectional ply.</p> <p>Inter-fiber failure mode A</p> <p>In this mode, the matrix fails in tension. Mathematically this is written as: $\sigma_2 \geq 0$.</p> <p>The expression for the matrix failure index, F_m is:</p> $F_m = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{S}\right)^2 + \left(1 - P_{\perp\parallel}^+ \frac{Y_T}{S}\right)^2 \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{Y_T}\right)^2} + P_{\perp\parallel}^+ \frac{\sigma_2}{S} \leq 1$ <p>where</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Y_T is the tensile stress allowable in direction 2 of the unidirectional ply. • S is the shear strength of the unidirectional ply given by: $S = Y_C/2$. • Y_C is the compressive stress allowable in direction 2 of the unidirectional ply. <p>Inter-fiber failure mode B</p> <p>The matrix fails in this mode if the following two conditions are met:</p> <p>The matrix fails in compression. Mathematically this is written as: $\sigma_2 < 0$ and the following equation is true:</p> $0 \leq \left \frac{\sigma_2}{\tau_{12}} \right \leq \frac{R_{\perp\perp}^A}{ \tau_{21c} }$ <p>where</p> $R_{\perp\perp}^A = \frac{S}{2P_{\perp\parallel}^-} \left(\sqrt{1 + 2P_{\perp\parallel}^- \frac{Y_C}{S}} - 1 \right)$ $\tau_{21c} = S \sqrt{1 + 2P_{\perp\parallel}^-}$ $P_{\perp\perp}^- = P_{\perp\parallel}^- \frac{R_{\perp\perp}^A}{S}$ <p>Failure Index</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The expression for the matrix failure index, F_m is: $F_m = \frac{1}{S} \left(\sqrt{\tau_{12}^2 + \left(P_{\perp\parallel}^- \sigma_2\right)^2} + P_{\perp\parallel}^- \sigma_2 \right) \leq 1$ <p>Inter-fiber failure mode C</p> <p>The matrix fails in this mode if $\sigma_2 < 0$ and the following equation is satisfied:</p> $0 \leq \left \frac{\tau_{12}}{\sigma_2} \right \leq \frac{ \tau_{21c} }{R_{\perp\perp}^A}$ <p>The expression for the matrix failure index, F_m is:</p> $F_m = \left[\left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{2(1 + P_{\perp\perp}^-) S} \right)^2 + \left(\frac{\sigma_2}{Y_C} \right)^2 \right] \frac{Y_C}{(-\sigma_2)} \leq 1$
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	<p>The Puck criterion is recommended by the DNV-GL ST 0376 Standard which also recommends partial safety factors for materials depending on the level of fidelity of the analysis.</p>

2.7 Models for Design and analysis of intra-modular joints and repairs

MODA
MOdelling Data providing a description
for Models for Design and analysis of intra-modular joints and repairs – Task3.6
CARBO4POWER

Clara Valero, ITAINNOVA, cvalero@itainnova.es

OVERVIEW of the SIMULATION			
1	USER CASE	The objective is to estimate the strength of different joints and repairs to find the most suitable design for each analysed case. The analysis will be focused on three different scenarios. i)intra-module joints ii)inter-module joints and iii)repairs using patches. The mechanical responses to be analysed will cover the elastic properties and the strengths of the joints/repairs (from the stress-strain curves in different material directions).	
2	MODELS	MODEL 1 - CONT	CONTINUOUS MODEL of Intra-module joints. Solid mechanics model for the simulation at coupon level.
		MODEL 2 - CONT	CONTINUOUS MODEL of Inter-module joints. Solid mechanics model for the simulation at coupon level.
		MODEL 3 - CONT	CONTINUOUS MODEL of Repairs using patches. Solid mechanics model for the simulation at specimen level.
		DATA MINING METHODOLOGY	N/A
3	PUBLICATION PEER-REVIEWING THE DATA	N/A	
4	ACCESS CONDITIONS	Available for CARBO4POWER partners or third parties under request.	
5	WORKFLOW AND ITS RATIONALE	The models will be used independently to estimate the system strength. They will be linked with the global models of the blades, from which the loads will be determined depending on the joint/repair location (for example through submodelling techniques).	

Workflow picture

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Figure 2.7 Workflow of Models for Design and analysis of intra-modular joints and repairs – Task3.6

MODA

Models for Design and analysis of intra-modular joints and repairs

Simulation with MODEL 1 – CONT: Intra-module joints

1 ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED		
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	The model will be used to simulate typical structural bonded joints used in blades considering the incorporation of Functionally Graded Adhesives (FGA), giving support to the design of this type of joints. The model will be focused on intra-modular bonded joints (i.e. between the skins or joining the skins and the webs). In some cases, the results obtained from this model will be correlated with the ones obtained from experimental tests for validation.
1.2	MATERIAL	Substrates made of different materials (FRP with different reinforcements configurations/lay-ups: UD, biaxial, quatriaxial...) and the adhesive with homogeneous or graded properties.
1.3	GEOMETRY	Small/medium scale prototypes representative of specific zones/sections.
1.4	TIME LAPSE	Seconds (quasi-static analysis).
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE	Service conditions: loads over the sections derived from the global models considering standard design/testing loads. These loads will produce locally in the joints Mode I, II or Mixed Mode loads.

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	CONDITIONS	
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	N/A

2 GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION		
2.1	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	CONTINUUM MODEL. Continuum solid mechanics. Simulation of structural failure of the joints based on cohesive elements.
2.2	MODEL ENTITY	Finite elements
2.3	MODEL PHYSICS/ CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	Equation PE Conservation laws 1. PE1: Mass conservation equation (continuity equation): $\dot{\rho} + \rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0$ 2. PE2: Linear Momentum Balance $\rho \dot{\mathbf{v}} - \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} - \rho \mathbf{b} = 0$ 3. PE3: Angular Momentum Balance $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^T$ 4. PE4: Energy Balance $\rho \dot{e} - \boldsymbol{\sigma} : (\nabla \mathbf{v}) + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} - \rho s = 0$
		Physical quantities Physics quantities of PE1 to PE4: ρ is the mass density, \mathbf{v} is the velocity, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress, \mathbf{b} is the body force per unit mass, e is the internal energy per unit mass, \mathbf{q} is the heat flux vector and s is the energy source per unit mass.
2.4	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation 1. MR1: Compatibility conditions $\nabla \times \mathbf{F} = \mathbf{0} \text{ finite strains}$ $\nabla \times (\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \mathbf{0} \text{ small strains}$ 2. MR2: Constitutive equations Additive decomposition of the strain rate $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{el} + \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{pl}$ Elasticity $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{D} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{el}$ Plasticity: Yield function, flow rule and hardening parameters evolution. $f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \theta, H_\alpha) = 0$ $d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{pl} = d\lambda \frac{\partial g(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \theta, H_\alpha)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ $dH_\alpha = d\lambda h_\alpha(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \theta, H_\alpha)$ Traction-separation laws for cohesive elements $\begin{cases} \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{K}' \boldsymbol{\delta} \text{ if } \boldsymbol{\sigma} < \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{crit} \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{K}' \boldsymbol{\delta} (1 - d) \text{ if } \boldsymbol{\sigma} > \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{crit} \end{cases}$

		Physical quantities/ descriptors for each MR	1. In MR1: \mathbf{F} is the deformation gradient, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the strain 2. In MR2: $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$ is the total strain rate, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{el}$ is the elastic strain rate, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{pl}$ is the plastic strain rate, \mathbf{D} is the stiffness tensor, f is the yield function, θ is the temperature, H_α are the hardening parameters, $d\lambda$ is the rate of change of plastic flow, g is the flow potential, h_α is the hardening law for H_α and σ and ε are the stress and strain respectively (for the last, differentiated between elastic and plastic). In addition, for the cohesive laws, δ is the separation, K is the penalty stiffness and d is the damage parameter.
2.5	PHYSICS FORMULATION OF THE CONDITIONS	Conditions obtained from global models for the blades or representing the ones that will be applied for the small/medium scale validation tests.	
2.6	SIMULATED INPUT	Fields of stresses / strains / displacements (depending on the approach) obtained from full scale models.	

3	SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS		
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Implicit Finite Element Method.	
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	Abaqus (http://www.3ds.com/es/productos-y-servicios/simulia)	
3.3	TIME STEP	Required for convergence of the Newton iterative method resolution of the non-linear equations.	
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL	PE1+PE2 equilibrium equations are expressed in its weak form (virtual work principle). PE5: Virtual Work Principle $\int_V \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \delta \mathbf{D} dV = \int_S \delta \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{t} dS + \int_V \delta \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{f} dV$ $\mathbf{t} = \mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}$ Physics quantities of this PE5: \mathbf{D} is the strain rate, \mathbf{v} is the velocity, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress, \mathbf{f} is the body force per unit volume, \mathbf{t} is surface traction per unit area. The equation PE5 is discretized and finally take the form of a set of algebraic equations in the form of: $[K]\{q\} = \{F\}$ Where $[K]$ is the system stiffness matrix, $\{q\}$ is the vector of nodal forces and $\{F\}$ is the vector of nodal forces. Material Relations: Incremental formulation is used for the elasto-plasticity. Material: The microstructure is discretized in a finite element mesh. The joints failure will be modelled through the utilization of cohesive elements.
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	Displacements, stresses or strains obtained from global models or reproducing the small/medium scale experimental tests.	
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	Non linear geometric calculations. Viscosity introduced for damage stabilization (if necessary).	

4 POST PROCESSING		
4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	Strength of the intra-module joint based on damage parameter of the cohesive elements.
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	Identification of elements of the joint with full damage.
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	Based on previous experiences, maximum error of around 30% is expected for these simulations.

Simulation with MODEL 2 – CONT: inter-module joints

1 ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED		
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	This model will be used to simulate modules transitions considering hybrid technologies (mechanical fasteners/inserts + bonding), giving support to the design of this type of joints. The objective is to evaluate different strategies to identify the most suitable ones. In some cases the results obtained from this model will be correlated with the ones obtained from experimental tests for validation.
1.2	MATERIAL	Substrates made of different materials (FRP with different reinforcements configurations/lay-ups: UD, biaxial, quatriaxial...) and the adhesive with homogeneous or graded properties. Mechanical fasteners/inserts made of metal.
1.3	GEOMETRY	Small/medium scale prototypes representative of specific zones/sections of the blades (from T3.5).
1.4	TIME LAPSE	Seconds (quasi-static analysis).
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	Service conditions: loads over the sections derived from the global models considering standard design/testing loads. These loads will produce locally in the joints Mode I, II or Mixed Mode loads.
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	N/A

2 GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION		
2.1	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	CONTINUUM MODEL. Continuum solid mechanics. Simulation of structural failure of the joints.
2.2	MODEL ENTITY	Finite elements
2.3	MODEL PHYSICS/CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	<p>Equation</p> <p>PE Conservation laws</p> <p>1. PE1. Mass conservation equation (continuity equation):</p> $\dot{\rho} + \rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0$ <p>2. PE2: Linear Momentum Balance</p> $\rho \dot{\mathbf{v}} - \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} - \rho \mathbf{b} = 0$ <p>3. PE3: Angular Momentum Balance</p>

			$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^T$ <p>4. PE4: Energy Balance</p> $\rho \dot{e} - \boldsymbol{\sigma} : (\nabla \boldsymbol{v}) + \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{q} - \rho s = 0$
		Physical quantities	Physics quantities of PE1 to PE4: ρ is the mass density, \boldsymbol{v} is the velocity, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress, \boldsymbol{b} is the body force per unit mass, e is the internal energy per unit mass, \boldsymbol{q} is the heat flux vector and s is the energy source per unit mass.
2.4	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation	<p>1. MR1: Compatibility conditions</p> $\nabla \times \boldsymbol{F} = \mathbf{0} \text{ finite strains}$ $\nabla \times (\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \mathbf{0} \text{ small strains}$ <p>2. MR2: Constitutive equations</p> <p>Additive decomposition of the strain rate</p> $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{el} + \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{pl}$ <p>Elasticity</p> $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{D} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{el}$ <p>Plasticity: Yield function, flow rule and hardening parameters evolution.</p> $f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \theta, H_\alpha) = 0$ $d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{pl} = d\lambda \frac{\partial g(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \theta, H_\alpha)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ $dH_\alpha = d\lambda h_\alpha(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \theta, H_\alpha)$
		Physical quantities/ descriptors for each MR	<p>1. In MR1: \boldsymbol{F} is the deformation gradient, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the strain</p> <p>2. In MR2: $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$ is the total strain rate, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{el}$ is the elastic strain rate, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{pl}$ is the plastic strain rate, \boldsymbol{D} is the stiffness tensor, f is the yield function, θ is the temperature, H_α are the hardening parameters, $d\lambda$ is the rate of change of plastic flow, g is the flow potential, h_α is the hardening law for H_α.</p>
2.5	PHYSICS FORMULATION OF THE CONDITIONS	Conditions obtained from global or specific models for the blades or representing the ones that will be applied for the small/medium scale validation tests.	
2.6	SIMULATED INPUT	Fields of stresses / strains / displacements (depending on the approach) obtained from full scale models. <i>Blades zones and sections will be defined according to the results obtained in T3.5</i>	

3	SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS		
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Implicit Finite Element Method.	
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	Abaqus (http://www.3ds.com/es/productos-y-servicios/simulia)	
3.3	TIME STEP	Required for convergence of the Newton iterative method resolution of the non linear equations.	
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL	PE1+PE2 equilibrium equations are expressed in its weak form (virtual work principle). PE5: Virtual Work Principle
		$\int_V \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \delta \boldsymbol{D} dV = \int_S \delta \boldsymbol{v} \cdot \boldsymbol{t} dS + \int_V \delta \boldsymbol{v} \cdot \boldsymbol{f} dV$	

			$t = n \cdot \sigma$ <p>Physics quantities of this PE5: D is the strain rate, v is the velocity, σ is the Cauchy stress, f is the body force per unit volume, t is surface traction per unit area.</p> <p>The equation PE5 is discretized and finally take the form of a set of algebraic equations in the form of:</p> $[K]\{q\} = \{F\}$ <p>Where $[K]$ is the system stiffness matrix, $\{q\}$ is the vector of nodal forces and $\{F\}$ is the vector of nodal forces.</p> <p>Material Relations: Incremental formulation is used for the elasto-plasticity.</p> <p>Material: The microstructure is discretized in a finite element mesh.</p>
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	Displacements, stresses or strains obtained from global models or reproducing the small/medium scale experimental tests.	
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	Non linear geometric calculations. Viscosity introduced for damage stabilization (if necessary).	

4	POST PROCESSING	
4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	Strength of the inter-module joint.
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	Identification of elements of the joint with full damage.
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	Based on previous experiences, maximum error of around 30% is expected for these simulations.

Simulation with MODEL 3 – CONT: Repairs using patches

1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED	
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	This model will simulate repairs using fully compatible 3R patches that can be cured and/or consolidated. The objective is to evaluate the performance and efficiency of the repairs compared to the undamaged material without repair. The mechanical performance of the patches will be tested by through mechanical tests such as tensile and/or bending tests. In some cases, the results obtained from this model will be correlated with the ones obtained from experimental tests.
1.2	MATERIAL	Substrates made of different materials (FRP with different reinforcements configurations/lays: UD, biaxial, quatriaxial...) and the adhesive with homogeneous or graded properties.
1.3	GEOMETRY	Small/medium scale prototypes representative of specific zones/sections. Different patch sizes and shapes (scarf angle, etc).
1.4	TIME LAPSE	Seconds (quasi-static analysis).
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	Service conditions: loads over the sections derived from the global models considering standard design/testing loads. These loads will produce locally in the joints Mode I, II or Mixed Mode loads.
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	N/A

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2		GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION	
2.1	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	CONTINUUM MODEL. Continuum solid mechanics. Simulation of structural failure of the joints based on cohesive elements.	
2.2	MODEL ENTITY	Finite elements	
2.3	MODEL PHYSICS/ CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	Equation	PE Conservation laws 1. PE1: Mass conservation equation (continuity equation): $\dot{\rho} + \rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0$ 2. PE2: Linear Momentum Balance $\rho \dot{\mathbf{v}} - \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} - \rho \mathbf{b} = 0$ 3. PE3: Angular Momentum Balance $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^T$ 4. PE4: Energy Balance $\rho \dot{e} - \boldsymbol{\sigma} : (\nabla \mathbf{v}) + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{q} - \rho s = 0$
		Physical quantities	Physics quantities of PE1 to PE4: ρ is the mass density, \mathbf{v} is the velocity, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress, \mathbf{b} is the body force per unit mass, e is the internal energy per unit mass, \mathbf{q} is the heat flux vector and s is the energy source per unit mass.
2.4	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation	1. MR1: Compatibility conditions $\nabla \times \mathbf{F} = \mathbf{0} \text{ finite strains}$ $\nabla \times (\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \mathbf{0} \text{ small strains}$ 2. MR2: Constitutive equations Additive decomposition of the strain rate $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}} = \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{el} + \dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{pl}$ Elasticity $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{D} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{el}$ Plasticity: Yield function, flow rule and hardening parameters evolution. $f(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \theta, H_\alpha) = 0$ $d\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}_{pl} = d\lambda \frac{\partial g(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \theta, H_\alpha)}{\partial \boldsymbol{\sigma}}$ $dH_\alpha = d\lambda h_\alpha(\boldsymbol{\sigma}, \theta, H_\alpha)$ Traction-separation laws for cohesive elements $\begin{cases} \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{K}' \boldsymbol{\delta} \text{ if } \boldsymbol{\sigma} < \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{crit} \\ \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{K}' \boldsymbol{\delta} (\mathbf{1} - \mathbf{d}) \text{ if } \boldsymbol{\sigma} > \boldsymbol{\sigma}_{crit} \end{cases}$
		Physical quantities/ descriptors for each MR	1. In MR1: \mathbf{F} is the deformation gradient, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}$ is the strain 2. In MR2: $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}$ is the total strain rate, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{el}$ is the elastic strain rate, $\dot{\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}}^{pl}$ is the plastic strain rate, \mathbf{D} is the stiffness tensor, f is the yield function, θ is the temperature, H_α are the hardening parameters, $d\lambda$ is the rate of change of plastic flow, g is the flow potential, h_α is the hardening law for H_α . In addition, for the cohesive laws, $\boldsymbol{\delta}$ is the separation, \mathbf{K} is the penalty stiffness and \mathbf{d} is the damage parameter.
2.5	PHYSICS FORMULATION OF	Conditions obtained from global models for the blades or representing the ones that will be applied for the small/medium scale validation tests.	

	THE CONDITIONS	
2.6	SIMULATED INPUT	Fields of stresses / strains / displacements (depending on the approach) obtained from full scale models.

3 SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS		
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Implicit Finite Element Method.
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	Abaqus (http://www.3ds.com/es/productos-y-servicios/simulia)
3.3	TIME STEP	Required for convergence of the Newton iterative method resolution of the non linear equations.
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	<p>PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL</p> <p>PE1+PE2 equilibrium equations are expressed in its weak form (virtual work principle). PE5: Virtual Work Principle</p> $\int_V \boldsymbol{\sigma} : \delta \mathbf{D} dV = \int_S \delta \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{t} dS + \int_V \delta \mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{f} dV$ $\mathbf{t} = \mathbf{n} \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma}$ <p>Physics quantities of this PE5: \mathbf{D} is the strain rate, \mathbf{v} is the velocity, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress, \mathbf{f} is the body force per unit volume, \mathbf{t} is surface traction per unit area.</p> <p>The equation PE5 is discretized and finally take the form of a set of algebraic equations in the form of:</p> $[K]\{q\} = \{F\}$ <p>Where $[K]$ is the system stiffness matrix, $\{q\}$ is the vector of nodal forces and $\{F\}$ is the vector of nodal forces.</p> <p>Material Relations: Incremental formulation is used for the elasto-plasticity.</p> <p>Material: The microstructure is discretized in a finite element mesh.</p> <p>The interlaminar failure will be modelled through the utilization of cohesive elements.</p>
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	Displacements, stresses or strains obtained from global models or reproducing the small/medium scale experimental tests.
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	Non linear geometric calculations. Viscosity introduced for damage stabilization (if necessary).

4 POST PROCESSING		
4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	Strength of the intra-module joint based on damage parameter of the cohesive elements.
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	Identification of elements of the joint with full damage.
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	Based on previous experiences, maximum error of around 30% is expected for these simulations.

2.8 Models for Design and analysis of prototypes, demonstrators and full blades analyses

MODA
MOdelling DAta providing a description
for Design and analysis of prototypes, demonstrators and full blades analyses – T3.7
CARBO4POWER

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OVERVIEW of the SIMULATION			
1	USER CASE	The goal is to estimate the working status of the designed wind blades and predict the structural critical area on them. The focus is on the morphology and internal structure of the wind blade. The purpose is to analyse the effect of the shapes of the wind blades on the rotating speed and pressure distributions, and the effect of the internal structure on the blade deformations. The mechanics to be studied will cover the turbulent flows, fluid-solid interactions, and the strengths.	
2	CHAIN OF MODELS	MODEL 1 - CFD MODEL	TURBULENCE MODEL. Turbulence model applied to the external domain surrounding the wind blade, which drives the wind blade and it is affected by its geometry.
		MODEL 2 – TRANSIENT STRUCTURAL	TRANSIENT STRUCTURAL MODEL. Transient structural model with elasticity used to simulate the deformation of the wind blade.
3	PUBLICATION PEER-REVIEWING THE DATA	N/A	
4	ACCESS CONDITIONS	Available for University of Strathclyde partner or third parties under request.	
5	WORKFLOW AND ITS RATIONALE	A coupled simulation strategy is proposed because the turbulence flow condition is highly affected by the morphology of the wind blade and the wind blade deformation is subjected to the pressure distribution. The CFD analysis (Model 1) requires the use of the deformed blade morphology from the transient structural simulation (Model 2) and the results of the surface pressures are used as inputs for updating the structural analysis (Model 2).	

Figure 2.8 Workflow of Design and analysis of prototypes, demonstrators and full blades analyses – T3.7

Elements in the simulation of Model 1 – CFD: turbulence model

1		ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	A dynamic fluid system (3D CFD analysis) consisting of the external morphology of the wind blade (WTB) and the surrounding area. A detailed analysis of the flow fields around the wind blade and the pressures on the wind blade surface. The pressures applied on the surface of the wind blades will be obtained and the information will be incorporated into the structural analysis.
1.2	MATERIAL	Air flows around the WTB. The material of the WTB is not relevant for this simulation.
1.3	GEOMETRY	Geometry of the WTB. The blade is modelled as free rotating walls in this simulation.
1.4	TIME LAPSE	
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	Wind conditions - imposed as a velocity inlet (wind speed at the WTB). Centre of rotation needs to be defined, which indicates the rotating axis of the wind turbine. Moment of inertia affects the rotating speed of the wind blade.
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	

2		GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION
2.1	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Continuum model - Turbulent fluid mechanics
2.2	MODEL ENTITY	Finite volumes
2.3	MODEL PHYSICS/	Equation Navier – Stokes equations for single phase turbulence flow:

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	CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE		1. Conservation equation of mass. $\rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} = 0$ 2. Conservation equation of momentum. $\rho \frac{\mathbf{u}}{t} + \rho(\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla)\mathbf{u} = \nabla \cdot [-p\mathbf{I} + \mu(\nabla\mathbf{u} + (\nabla\mathbf{u})^T)] + \mathbf{F}$
		Physical quantities	1. Density, ρ 2. Velocity vector, \mathbf{u} 3. Pressure, p 4. Volume force vector, \mathbf{F} 5. Dynamic viscosity, μ
2.4	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation	Newtonian fluid has a linear relationship between stress and strain. 1. $\tau = 2\mu\mathbf{S} - \frac{2}{3}\mu(\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u})\mathbf{I}$ 2. $\mathbf{S} = \frac{1}{2}(\nabla\mathbf{u} + (\nabla\mathbf{u})^T)$
		Physical quantities/ descriptors for each MR	1. Viscous stress tensor, τ 2. Dynamic viscosity, μ 3. Strain-rate tensor, \mathbf{S} Velocity vector, \mathbf{u}
2.5	SIMULATED INPUT	The deformed geometry calculated from model 2 will be used to update the morphology of the wind blade for the calculation.	

3 SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS		
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Pressure-Based Segregated solver. The constraint of mass conservation (continuity) of the velocity field is achieved by solving a pressure (or pressure correction) equation. The pressure equation is derived from the continuity and the momentum equations in such a way that the velocity field, corrected by the pressure, satisfies the continuity.
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	ANSYS Fluent
3.3	TIME STEP	1 ms
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL Equations presented in sections 2.3 and 2.4 written up for the entity in the model. 1 equation for continuity, flux integration over the faces of a control volume (integral form replaced by summation of flux terms at each face) 1 semi-discretized equation for momentum, applied to a control volume (Gaussian divergence theorem to replace the volume integrals over the control volume by surface integrals over the control surface)
3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	Wind speed which drives the wind turbine rotating speed. The external morphology of the turbine is used as dynamic wall Periodicities are to be included when a single blade is simulated?
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	N/A

4 POST PROCESSING		
4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	<p>The drag force component along the direction opposite to the relative motion of WTB is computed by summing the dot product of the pressure and viscous forces on each face of WTB with the direction vector.</p> <p>The lift force component along the direction perpendicular to the oncoming flow is computed by summing the dot product of the pressure and viscous forces on each face of WTB with the direction vector.</p> <p>The associated force coefficients are computed for WTB, using the reference values. The force coefficient is defined as force divided by $\frac{1}{2}\rho v^2 A$, where ρ, v, and A are the density, velocity, and area.</p> <p>The information concerning the pressure profiles will be used as a simulated input for the model 2. The results can be exported back to the simulation software to plot the profiles of the pressure and velocity fields for studying the flow pattern.</p>
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	<p>The 6 DOF solver in ANSYS FLUENT uses the object's forces and moments in order to compute the translational and angular motion of the centre of gravity of an object. The angular motion of the object, $\dot{\vec{w}}_B$, is computed using body coordinates:</p> $\dot{\vec{w}}_B = L^{-1} \left(\sum \vec{M}_B - \vec{w}_B \times L \vec{w}_B \right)$ <p>L is the inertia tensor, \vec{M}_B is the moment vector of the body, and \vec{w}_B is the rigid body angular velocity vector</p>
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	Based on previous experiences, error of around 20-30% is expected for these simulations.

Elements in the simulation of Model 2 – Transient structural model

1 ASPECT OF THE USER CASE/SYSTEM TO BE SIMULATED		
1.1	ASPECT OF THE USER CASE TO BE SIMULATED	<p>A large sized blade subjected to aerodynamic forces, gravity and inertial loads. A detailed analysis of the stress and strain field for the whole structure of the blade.</p> <p>The pressures applied on the surface will be obtained from the turbulent fluid analysis and the deformation of the blade will feed back to the CFD model.</p>
1.2	MATERIAL	carbon fibre composite, glass fibre composite and adhesive
1.3	GEOMETRY	Geometry of the WTB
1.4	TIME LAPSE	Minutes.
1.5	MANUFACTURING PROCESS OR IN-SERVICE CONDITIONS	<p>Centre of rotation needs to be defined, which indicates the rotating axis of the wind turbine.</p> <p>Moment of inertia affects the rotating speed of the wind blade.</p> <p>Wind conditions, from the pressures obtained from model 1.</p>
1.6	PUBLICATION ON THIS DATA	

2		GENERIC PHYSICS OF THE MODEL EQUATION	
2.1	MODEL TYPE AND NAME	Transient structural analysis	
2.2	MODEL ENTITY	Finite element	
2.3	MODEL PHYSICS/ CHEMISTRY EQUATION PE	Equation	PE Conservation laws 1. PE1: Mass conservation equation (continuity equation): $\dot{\rho} + \rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{v} = 0$ 2. PE2: Linear Momentum Balance $\rho \dot{\mathbf{v}} - \nabla \cdot \boldsymbol{\sigma} - \rho \mathbf{b} = 0$ 3. PE3: Angular Momentum Balance $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \boldsymbol{\sigma}^T$
		Physical quantities	Physics quantities of PE1 to PE3: ρ is the mass density, \mathbf{v} is the velocity, $\boldsymbol{\sigma}$ is the Cauchy stress, \mathbf{b} is the body force per unit mass
2.4	MATERIALS RELATIONS	Relation	1. MR1: Compatibility conditions $\nabla \times \mathbf{F} = \mathbf{0}$ finite strains $\nabla \times (\nabla \times \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}) = \mathbf{0}$ small strains 2. MR2: Constitutive equations Elasticity $\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \mathbf{D} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{el}$
		Physical quantities/ descriptors for each MR	\mathbf{F} is the deformation gradient, $\boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^{el}$ is the strain; \mathbf{D} is the stiffness tensor,
2.5	SIMULATED INPUT	The surface pressure/gravity/inertial loads will be input from Model 1.	

3		SOLVER AND COMPUTATIONAL TRANSLATION OF THE SPECIFICATIONS	
3.1	NUMERICAL SOLVER	Full-solution method solver. The constitutive equations of materials and the geometry of the blade are processed to form mass matrix and damping matrix, iteratively solved to satisfy the motion equation; it is updated/repeated at each time increment.	
3.2	SOFTWARE TOOL	ANSYS Mechanical	
3.3	TIME STEP	Automatically controlled, at 1ms level	
3.4	COMPUTATIONAL REPRESENTATION	PHYSICS EQUATION, MATERIAL RELATIONS, MATERIAL	The equation PE1 to PE3 are discretized and finally take the form of a set of algebraic equations in the form of: $M u''(t) + C u'(t) + F^i(t) = F^a(t)$ Where M is structural mass matrix, C is structural damping matrix, $u''(t)$ is nodal acceleration vector, $u'(t)$ is nodal velocity vector, $F^i(t)$ is internal load vector and $F^a(t)$ is applied load vector. Material is discretized in a finite element mesh.

3.5	COMPUTATIONAL BOUNDARY CONDITIONS	Rotating speed of the wind turbine The aerodynamic pressure load Direction of gravity Constraints of the blade root
3.6	ADDITIONAL SOLVER PARAMETERS	N/A

4	POST PROCESSING	
4.1	THE PROCESSED OUTPUT	Deformation field will be extracted / calculated along the span direction of the blade. Stress field will be processed to find hot spots. The stress results will be checked against material's fatigue S-N curves to determine the structure's service life. The deformation and stress results will feed back to structure optimization to achieve multidisciplinary objectives.
4.2	METHODOLOGIES	The deformation data and stress data will be sampled element by element and then summarized.
4.3	MARGIN OF ERROR	Based on previous experiences the margin of error can be of around 15%

3 Deviations from DoA

There are no significant deviations to be reported. The technical work has been carried out according to the approach and the timeline proposed in the DoA.

4 Next plans

Modelling and simulation activities will be carried out during the duration of the project based on the workflows established in the MODA sheets. These documents/fiches can be updated/modified during the project execution if needed.

5 Conclusions

In this deliverable the MODA sheets corresponding to the modelling activities of Carbo4Power WP3 have been compiled. Before month 7 of the Carbo4Power project, all the partners involved in simulation tasks have completed the MODA fiches. The development of these documents has helped in the definition of the models that will be used and in the identification of the inputs and outputs of each simulation task. In addition, links between all the models have been identified to have a better understanding of the overall simulation workflow in Carbo4Power and the interactions with other activities/WPs.

